

Computer Assisted Interpreting Systems

Research development study

2022

The primary objective of the CASSIS (Computer Assisted Interpretation System) project's research team is to carry out an R&D study for the development of a computer-assisted, technology-based integrated system for interpreting. The support will primarily assist the interpreter in his/her daily work in **simultaneous interpreting** and secondarily in **consecutive** interpreting.

Here is a quote about the relationship between knowledge and the computer:

"Scientific knowledge is knowledge that we understand to such a depth that we can teach it to a computer. Until we fully understand something, it's a kind of art to do it. An algorithm, a computer program, provides a more useful way than anything else to test our knowledge. In interpreting, moving from art to science means learning how to automate something." (Szakadát, 2007). Conference interpreting involves elements that cannot be algorithmised at every step and therefore cannot be fully automated.

The aim of the study is to explore the relevant parts of the scientific background for the implementation of the idea. How the principles of the system we envisage can be integrated into existing theory. What feedback can be expected from its application. How the theory can be used to improve interpreting support, and how the system under development might affect specific parts of the theory.

Our research is based on the premise that while technological innovations to support translation/translation are a daily occurrence - having been an integral and indispensable part of the daily work of (professional) translators for more than two

decades - technology services to support interpreting were only theoretical at the time of the submission of the application.

In the field of interpreting, on the other hand, less constructive opinions, which clearly foresee the rapid rise of machine interpreting and the reluctance of interpreters to use computers in their work, are expressed much more frequently.

The advent of machine interpreting is currently only working satisfactorily in very clearly delimited communication situations, and only if everything goes according to plan. Such an interpreting device can only recognise phrases and sentences predefined in its database by means of its speech recognition software and then "pronounce" the most appropriate one in its database by machine voice. As a consequence, it cannot correctly interpret unexpected, humorous, ironic or non-literal utterances. Thus, machine interpreters will probably never be able to cover the entire interpreting market, but rather (like machine translation) will probably only be a simpler, cheaper, but lower-quality and much less reliable alternative in certain communication situations (Horváth 2013b, Seresi 2016).

The rapid expansion of neural machine translation has become fully accepted by translators due to its even faster-developing technologies.

Our research team's approach is quite different: we believe that human interpretation is needed in many communication situations and that this will not change fundamentally in the future. Accordingly, our research is based more on the premise that we need to channel the benefits and opportunities offered by technological innovations into supporting interpreters in their everyday work: our project is precisely to explore the potential of this type of support. And, in the process, to implement a prototype of the support system.

The story of the idea:

His Holiness the 14th Dalai Lama gave a lecture in Budapest on 18 and 19 September 2010. Sándor Hajós participated in the series together with Katalin Hajós. As practicing interpreter-translators, they listened to the Dalai Lama's speech in consecutive interpretation in awe. The interpreter, Dr. Attila Kiss, is the official Hungarian interpreter of the Lama and currently the head of the Department of English Studies at the SZTE. The interpreter's performance was astonishing, interpreting 15-20 minute speeches with wonderful, complete Hungarian sentences, interspersed with quite specialised terminology.

That's when the idea was born to create something for interpreting that is similar to the CAT tools used for translation. It was only five years later that IT developments allowed the first version to be designed as a real model.

We focus our study on the following broad themes:

- 1. THE QUESTIONS POSED BY CASSIS**
- 2. THE JUSTIFICATION FOR THE SUPPORT PROVIDED BY CASSIS**
- 3. ON INTERPRETATION**
- 4. CASSIS AND MACHINE-ASSISTED INTERPRETATION**
- 5. THE TECHNOLOGICAL AND IT BACKGROUND OF CASSIS**
- 6. PROPOSALS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF CASSIS USING INFOCOMMUNICATION TOOLS**
- 7. THE CASSIS TESTING PROCESS**
- 8. OUR RESULTS**
- 9. CONCLUSION - BACK-CHECKING**
- 10. THE PERSPECTIVES OF CASSIS**

1 - THE QUESTIONS POSED BY CASSIS

If translation assistance works, there should also be a solution to support interpreters to make their work easier and faster, while improving their performance and the quality of their work.

It is a well-known fact that simultaneous interpretation relies on highly complex brain mechanisms. Simultaneous interpreting is a special case of speech perception and speech production, since during interpreting speech perception and speech production do not take place in the same language, but the two processes are almost simultaneous (see Horváth¹ - 1). The divided attention required for interpreting and the immediacy of the basic interpreting process (*real time activity*)

¹ Ildikó, Horváth: *Bevezetés a tolmácsolás pszichológiájába (Introduction to the Psychology of Interpreting)*, ELTE Eötvös Publishing House, 2015

make this linguistic mediation activity extremely difficult. We therefore seek to identify existing technological innovations that can be effectively incorporated into the interpreting process in a way that helps rather than hinders the interpreter in this highly complex task.

We envisage two basic functions of the interpreter support system: a real-time transcription of the speech being interpreted, combined with bilingual terminology support (from a terminology database pre-loaded into the system or available on the Internet). The following questions are addressed with regard to the viability of the system:

- does the solution described above help the interpreter through different information than usual or, on the contrary, divide his/her attention even further, thus making the cognitive processes involved in interpreting even more complex?
- the interpreter receives the transcription of the heard text in real time, allowing him/her practically to perform simultaneous interpreting concurrently with using text-assisted interpreting or the technique of sight-reading for language mediation. Does this process of language mediation represent a field entirely separate from simultaneous interpreting? Does it involve a more complex process? Does it simplify cognitive processes? What are its advantages? What are its disadvantages?
- does the terminological assistance in the target language facilitate a more precise formulation of the target language text, or does it slow down or complicate the cognitive processes involved in interpreting?

- or will being properly practiced in CASSIS and adapting one's interpreting strategy lead to a much better result?
- do immediate terminological hits make the target language more efficient and more polished, or on the contrary, confuse the interpreter and thus impair his/her performance?
- what effect does the use of CASSIS have on the interpreter's working memory? Does it relieve the workload or does it further overload it?
- in the medium term, will the psychological and cognitive workload and performance of CASSIS-supported simultaneous interpreters improve or deteriorate? In other words, how does CASSIS affect the interpreter's workload and quality of work?
- with sufficient theoretical preparation, practice, and the right work strategy, can application be made easier and the acceptance of this type of work improved?

In addition, of course, our research also seeks to answer other questions that touch upon the technical details of the interpreting process, but we will come to these later.

2. THE JUSTIFICATION FOR THE SUPPORT PROVIDED BY CASSIS

Our research aims to resolve the scientific and technological uncertainty that can be summarised in the following question:

is it possible to improve the work of simultaneous interpreters by a new method, different from the IT solutions already known, which integrates several technological achievements in a single prototype?

We aim to answer this question through our research and development activities. In this case, the aim of development is to create an interpreting support system under a new concept, including of course the creation of the programme, its testing and the subsequent integration of the results. The testing will allow the verification of the theorised potential and effectiveness of the system, and will provide an opportunity to verify its viability by measurement.

Therefore, one of the results of the project is the visual representation of the source language text to be interpreted via a speech recognition software, which is accompanied by a search in the terminology databases connected to the system by means of analysis modules (*morphological and syntactic analysers*) running in the background. As a result of the search, any technical term or multi-word term (terminology) occurring in the speech which the program finds in a built-in dictionary, terminology database or corpus is displayed in a clearly visible, dedicated window on the computer screen. The terminological assistance displayed supports the interpreter's search in his/her bilingual or multilingual mental lexicon, thus facilitating the retrieval of words/specialised words/concepts.

It is important to point out that, unlike translation, there is currently no such widespread computer support for interpretation. In the field of translation, there is now a wide range of computer tools to choose from, and machine translation methods are very widespread. However, the question of whether it is technically possible/feasible to support the interpreting process with computer tools in the similarly to translation support has not been widely researched or investigated.

Our project therefore aims to answer this question through

- a) developing the theoretical background for a new interpretation support tool / service,
- b) designing, building and testing such a tool, and
- c) measuring the impact of its use on the quality of interpretation.

An important point is that the scientific uncertainties that the project aims to resolve are all uncertainties that seemed hopeless to resolve before the advent of machine speech processing and without the current level of confidence in speech-to-text. This is partly what makes the proposed solution so novel, since it is not yet clear to what extent the technical tools which are increasingly used by interpreters, and which we propose in a very different way from those used hitherto, will support or hinder them in their work. The question therefore arises as to whether an integrated support tool specifically designed for interpreters would be more effective than a combination of separate computer tools that are available here and there but are not intrinsically linked.

The justification for our research is also justified by the fact that, despite the rapid pace of development in the technology sector, the literature on computer-assisted interpreting is extremely limited in relation to the actual scale of the problem. While today, computer-assisted translation and machine translation technology is advancing very rapidly, interpreters are currently only marginally supported by similar systems.

In addition, the project we are planning also includes differences to the already known translation support procedures and methods, which specifically support the

solution of other subtasks that arise during oral translation, which are not necessarily the case for written translation.

(Take, for example, the phenomenon of misinterpretation, which is not a problem in visual input-based translation, since the text to be translated is available to the translator in written form throughout the entire translation process. Importantly, while simultaneous interpretation is done in real time - and even in consecutive interpretation there is real-time feedback - in written translation the translator does not have to deal with such problems at all. Therefore, the creation of machine modules to be developed for these tasks within our project is fundamentally new compared to the traditional machine translation support toolbox.

Our research is also completely new in that it tries to combine several fields and use the results of each field to design our project: psycholinguistics, bionics, infobionics, linguistics, computer science, artificial intelligence, neuropsychology, neurolinguistics, etc.

3. ON INTERPRETATION

Although the field of interpreting research is relatively new, there are many theories and approaches to describe the complex process of interpreting, such as the central interpretive model, cognitive information processing models, the global, functionalist-linguistic approach, or even neuropsychological and neurolinguistic approaches. In addition, we can even read of neurophysiological approaches (Szabari 1999). These theories mostly capture the complexity of the interpreting process and aim to describe it from different perspectives.

As mentioned above, simultaneous interpreting is a special case of speech perception and speech production, because during interpreting speech perception and speech production do not take place in the same language, and the two processes occur almost simultaneously (Szabari 1999). Another important element of the process is the intention of speech: the simultaneous interpreter does not

express his/her own thoughts when interpreting, and thus does not convey his/her own intention of speech, but works according to an externally given "program". The motivation of the simultaneous interpreter is therefore indirect, not to satisfy his or her own communicative needs (Klaudy 2004).

Several other models explain this highly complex cognitive process: Chernov emphasises the role of long- and short-term anticipation (Chernov 2004), and Gile approaches the process of synchronous interpreting from the perspective of the management of available mental energy (Gile 1995). The work of Fabbro and Gran, who use neurolinguistics methods to investigate the mental processes of simultaneous interpreters, also contributes to a better understanding of the processes involved in simultaneous interpreting. A noteworthy aspect is that the latter two researchers have found that novice and practising simultaneous interpreters use different interpreting strategies: learners tend to interpret at the level of individual words (staying at word level), while practised interpreters focus on the delivery of meaning (this will be relevant in the CASSIS testing process, see later).

With our support system, we will change the process of interpreting. To do this, we will use interpreting models from previous research, which have always looked at the goal of interpreting from a practical point of view and the processes assumed to take place in the interpreter's brain to achieve it, but which are increasingly being studied. The models that are commonly known so far (Teodora Cekic 2017)

- Interpretative model
- Scientific school
- Cognitive-information processing model
- Cognitive-pragmatic model
- Effort model

Only two of the models are explained in more detail here, which will help to build the theoretical model of the CASSIS application.

Interpretative model

or the Paris School: the successful foundation of modern interpreter training laid down by two practising interpreters and academics (Seleskovitch, D., Lederer, M. 2002) is that the interpreter conveys deverbilized ideas, detached from the source language form. The first phase is the grasping of the sense: this is the phase of comprehension. The interpreter links the linguistic elements (the linguistic meaning of words and sentences) with his knowledge of the world (outside the language). The comprehension of linguistic elements is automatic, whereas the synthesis of knowledge is a conscious process. The comprehension phase is crucial for deverbilisation to take place properly, in the second phase. During this, the interpreter frees the thought from the bonds of the source language and continues to work with the interpreted thought (*sens*) and message, detached from the words. Deverbilisation protects the interpreter against interference. The third stage is the reconstruction of the text in the target language and, if deverbilisation is successful, the target language text is produced spontaneously without any special effort.

The expression of the message in the target language is now completely divorced from the structure of the source language text and conforms to the norms of the target language (Rohonyi 2018)

Gile's effort model

Daniel Gile (Gile 1997) developed his model more than twenty years ago, initially speculatively, for his students. It is based on the assumption that, for the difficult work of significant cognitive sub-tasks, interpreters have only a limited amount of existing mental capacity. He sought to explain why professional interpreters make mistakes (omissions, poor linguistic and grammatical formulations). These mistakes do not result from their lack of preparedness or knowledge. He built his description of the model on his conclusions: interpreting requires mental energy, once this is used up, performance deteriorates. Gile calls the brain process of interpreting effort because the time spent on the elements of the process tires the interpreter and drains his or her energy. According to Gile, simultaneous interpreting (SI) consists of three major energy-consuming processes: the first is the Listening and Analysis Effort (L), the second is the (speech) Production Effort (P), the third is the Short-term Memory Effort (M), and these are joined by the Coordination Effort (C), which is needed to coordinate the others.

Gile's effort model for SI (Gile 2009a):

$$SI = L + P + M + C$$

In other words, simultaneous interpreting (SI) is: listening (L) and analysis (P), memory use (M) and coordination (C). (Note that this is not a mathematical formula and addition.) Analysis and memory are also necessary for speech production.

The formula covers the processes and the effort required in the interpreter's brain from the time the speaker's source language speech reaches the interpreter's ear to the pronunciation of the interpreter's target language speech.

Eye-camera, EEG and psycho-physiological and neuro-physiological studies have empirically proven the model (Seeber 2017a). Such methods can be used to

compare which inputs the interpreter considers as primary and how much energy he or she devotes to them (Seeber 2017b). Research in this regard has already achieved numerous results. The conclusion can be drawn that it is primarily the individual's characteristics that play a decisive role.

The explanation of errors made by the interpreter, based on Gile's model of effort, is supported by psycho-physiological research.

In the speech production effort, Gile stresses that the difficulty lies in the fact that another speaker dictates both the amount and the pace of the incoming information. Waiting for the sentence to finish can overload short-term memory. The speaker's lexical and syntactic choices may help the interpreter, but following the source language structure is risky because of linguistic differences. The interpreter is forced to deviate from his/her speech production habits. All in all, the interpreter is best advised to formulate the target language text on the basis of the meaning.

The high demand on short-term memory is indicated by the "inclusion" of memory as effort in SI. Although the operations take only seconds, the operation cannot be automated. There are several reasons for the high strain on memory: firstly the time from the utterance of the source language speech to their processing, secondly the time elapsed until the formulation of the message in the target language, and thirdly the need for different strategies if the source language text is not easily understandable, and finally linguistic reasons (Gile 1995a, 2009a). The coordination effort is responsible for the interpreter's optimal allocation of capacity between listening and understanding, speech production and memory. CASSIS plans to make changes to the process described here. In order to use it correctly, the interpreter will need to change and practice his/her strategy.

Comprehending speech and written text

According to psycholinguistics, speech perception is, in a narrow sense, the very perceiving of speech, and in a broader sense, the understanding of speech. In the case of CASSIS and the pre-received written presentation text (text-assisted interpreting), this is complemented to some extent by text comprehension (text perception). It is the understanding of these complex processes, which take place in a short time, that brings us closer to understanding the interpreter's work.

In interpreting, comprehension goes well beyond speech recognition; probabilistic analysis and anticipation also takes place (Gile 2009a, Chernov 2004). If listening and reading as an effort is disturbed by phonetic, lexical or syntactic errors of the speaker (e.g. strong accent, speech rate, intonation), the basis for all other efforts is compromised and even experienced interpreters face serious challenges in producing coherent target language text under such circumstances (Kurz 2008: 182). Listening and analysis require more effort from the interpreter than from other conference participants, because the interpreter cannot listen selectively and has less background knowledge than experts in the field (Gile 2009a).

Speech recognition-understanding itself is, according to psycholinguistics, the recognition of speech sounds and sound relations on the one hand, and the understanding of words, sentences, and text on the other (Gósy 2005). This is where the mental lexicon, which can be considered a "brain dictionary", is used to compose the meaning of what is heard and seen. For further processes, the content thus understood is stored in another temporary area of the brain called "working memory". In the brain, the system of these processes is language-independent, anatomically identical for everyone. The operation depends on language. The big difference between the comprehension of spoken and written text in the brain, apart from the input, is that the latter involves segmentation, which makes it

somewhat easier to read. Segmentation is highly language-specific. Knowledge of languages is necessary, the depth of knowledge determines the perceptual processes. The speaker helps or hinders the listener or the interpreter in segmentation, the processing of what is said: by the tone of voice, articulation, melody, tempo, rhythm changes. These are also language-specific. Together, acoustics and the speaker's facial expressions have a helpful effect on comprehension.

Listening to speech and simultaneous visual inputs constitute multimodal perception. Visual input during interpreting includes reading, the partner/speaker's lip movements, visible tongue movements, facial expressions, eye movements, jaw movements, gestures, head movements, the raising and lowering of eyebrows, glances (Gósy 2005). In the case of CASSIS, visual input is complemented by on-screen speech tracking and terminology tracking.

A completely new field of research is investigating whether it is the auditory or the visual channel stimuli that takes precedence. In this context, the question for interpreters is the role of multimodal perception in source language comprehension and, through this, target language production (Korpál 2017, Seresi 2017, Seeber 2011, 2017b).

Fabbro and Gran found that both hemispheres play a role in the process of synchronous translation (Fabbro and Gran, 1994: 6).

² F., Fabbro, L., Gran, *English Neurological and neuropsychological aspects of polyglossia and simultaneous interpretation* in S., Lambert & B., Moser-Mercer (Eds.), BRIDGING THE GAP: EMPIRICAL RESEARCH IN SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETATION (pp. 273-317.), Amsterdam: Benjamins, 1994

Among the models describing the interpreting process, it is Gile's "effort model" that best fits the criteria of our research. It breaks down interpreting into sub-processes based on the multiple and diverse processes that take place in parallel. This model is interesting for CASSIS because it allows us precisely to achieve in practice a further subdivision of the basic processes of interpreting into sub-processes. According to Gile's model, the "science" of manoeuvring between processes can be developed through practice. Thus, a personal working strategy can be developed.

But what are the basic processes? What are the sub-processes? What exactly does a simultaneous interpreter do?

The task of a simultaneous interpreter is to translate speech in language A into language B in real time. Real time does not, of course, mean that the interpreter speaks at exactly the same time as the speaker, since there is a so-called "following distance" between the speaker and the interpreter (perception and understanding of text A, pronunciation of text B), i.e. *décalage*. *Décalage* is in practice a matter of seconds, and depends on complexity of the source language text, the frequency of specialised terminology (and, in connection with this, the interpreter's vocabulary and preparedness, the interpreter's work habits, memory, and state at the moment (how tired they are, and at which stage of the conference we are), what type of text they interpret (descriptive, appellative, informational, questions and answers in quick succession, etc.), the frequency of factual elements (numbers, proper names, etc.), the speaker's rhythm, accent, and so on. In a matter of seconds, the interpreter hears, interprets, anticipates, switches, speaks, checks back, and as a

result, the source-language text given by the speaker is transformed into the target-language text in seconds. The interpreter is therefore located between these two end points. As a matter of experience, the interpreter can work with a delay of about 10 to 12 seconds in order to interpret the speaker's speech in a meaningful way.

However, it should be remembered that the extremely high level of linguistic proficiency required in both working languages, a very broad active vocabulary and a very high level of technical interpreting skills are not enough to achieve the required quality, and that interpreters must also overcome a number of ad hoc difficulties at any given moment. These are listed in the context of the factors determining *décalage*, which may be supplemented by additional ad hoc difficulties. To summarise, in simultaneous interpreting, the interpreter faces the following difficulties in the complex workflow described above:

- Memorise and recall numbers accurately
- Understanding memorising and accurately recalling proper names (unfamiliar to the interpreter - personal names, institution names, geographical names and proper names in general) (accents, pronunciation of proper names in a language other than the speaker's mother tongue)
- Correct and complete reproduction of functions, positions, titles
- Abbreviations and acronyms (in this case, the first difficulty may arise if these abbreviations are language-specific and appear in the source text without being expanded /this can be further divided into two cases:
 - the interpreter knows the target language equivalent,

- does not know the equivalent; (the difficulty is that the interpreter has to produce the target language equivalent immediately)
- Idiomatic expressions
- Addressing people
- Panels
- Puns
- Quotes from
- Abstract, complex thoughts
- References requiring background knowledge
- Length, density, complexity of sentences/thoughts
- Text coherence (the relationship between speaker and speech intention has shifted)
- Specialist vocabulary and its frequency
- Speech rhythm
- Volume/sound quality
- Performer style/voice
- The fundamental syntactic differences in the structure of the source and target languages, i.e. the very different syntactic structure of the two languages (for example, in Romance languages the possessive structures are in reverse order compared to Hungarian; in German, the word order is much less bound than in Hungarian, so the predicate can be placed at the end of the sentence, while in Hungarian a thought/sentence is usually made sense of by the predicate. The interpreter must therefore have very good anticipation skills.)
- Accent of the performer

- Characteristics of interpretation technique (switching between languages quickly during question and answer; highly descriptive texts; impassioned speaker's unintelligible train of thought or appellative delivery; written structure, circular sentences read out without intonation; poor/monotone/jumping speaker; stressed, hurried, incoherent speaker, etc.)
- Lack of preparation by the interpreter (lack of time, carelessness, lack of preparation materials, passive language)
- Matching of culture-specific concept or specialist terminology
- Length of sequence to be transmitted (inappropriate switching between the two simultaneous interpreters)
- Other

One type of visual attention sharing is ***text-accompanied simultaneous interpreting*** (Rohonyi 2018³ - 5). As Rohonyi summarises (*see 5*), text-accompanied simultaneous interpreting does not only cover the process of listening comprehension and speech production, since in addition to the information received through the auditory channel, the interpreter also has access to a written version of the text through a visual channel. In general, if the interpreter receives the speaker's presentation material in advance, if the transcript of the text is received in good time before the interpreting event, the interpreter has the opportunity to familiarise himself with the text. The interpreter has the text in its

³ Borbála, Rohonyi, *A szöveggel támogatott szinkrontolmácsolás vizsgálata angol-magyar nyelvi irányban (Investigating text-assisted simultaneous interpreting in English-Hungarian)*, Doctoral School of Linguistics, ELTE, Budapest, 2018

entirety, has the opportunity to see/read it in its entirety and thus to familiarise himself with it, to understand its thought process, to learn the speaker's speech intention, i.e. to know where the speaker is starting from and where he wants to go in his presentation; he has the opportunity to consult experts beforehand and to prepare himself terminologically for the interpretation of the text (but he cannot know the accent, the rhythm of speech and the speaker's style of speaking in advance). However, it is most common for the interpreter to receive the written version of the speech a few minutes before the performance. He is then faced with a difficult decision: seeing an unfamiliar text, it is difficult to reconcile the spoken and written versions, which often do not overlap (*see later*). He or she occasionally looks at the text, even following it with his eyes during difficult passages, but it is difficult to manage both processes (simultaneous interpretation of unfamiliar spoken text and the simultaneous sight-reading of unfamiliar written text that does not match the former) at the same time. This is due to the different nature of the information channels (written input vs. auditory input, which requires different perceptual processes). The question is how to manage the information coming in through the auditory and visual channels at the same time, since the auditory channel is already used to monitor two types of speech: the source language speech of the speaker and his own production in the target language.

In sum, it would seem that, in the light of the above, text-assisted simultaneous interpreting is a completely different genre from simultaneous interpreting (Cammoun et al. 2009⁴, Lamberger-Felber and Schneider 2009⁵),

⁴ R., Cammoun, C., Davies, K. Ivanov., B. Naimushin, *Simultaneous Interpretation with Text: Is the Text 'Friend' or 'Foe'? Laying Foundations for a Teaching Module*. Observational research paper, 2009

⁵ H., Lamberger-Felber, J., Schneider, *Linguistic interference in simultaneous interpreting with text: A case study*, In: G., Hansen, A., Chesterman, H., Gerzymisch-Arbogast (eds), *Efforts and Models in Interpreting and Translation Research - A Tribute to Daniel Gile*, Amsterdam and Philadelphia, 2009

In a way, in the sense that CASSIS provides real-time display of the speaker's speech in written form, it can be considered as text-supported simultaneous interpreting.

To summarise, two main theories are in conflict when outlining the different processes of the brain (perception-deverbalisation-production) in models of the interpreting process. According to the theory of cerebral localisation (I), certain brain regions are responsible for performing specific operations in completely separate ways. This theory has been supported by computed tomography and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) studies, which suggest that each linguistic process has its own "execution area" in the brain (Navracsis 2014). Opposed to this is the anti-localisation theory (II), according to which, the brain is responsible for managing the various linguistic processes in an undisturbed manner as an integral whole. Both theories are currently accepted, i.e. the different linguistic sub-processes do have their place in the human brain, but it is essential for the very complex linguistic process to be carried out in a simultaneous and coordinated way.

The detailed processes of interpretation according to the models are shown in the table below:

Name of the process
Perception of source language text and environmental impact
Understanding the structure of source language text, sentence structure, and the speaker's intention
Understanding the terminology of a source text
Anticipation
Dividing attention, memorising
Recalling the appropriate target language terms
Accurate and complete reproduction of factual information (numbers, names, etc.) in the target language
Translating suprasegmental features of source text into target language
Creating the right sentence structure in the target language
Ensuring a steady, even speech rate and appropriate articulation
Maintaining the correct following distance from the source language text (<i>décalage</i>)
Continuous concentration

Stress management
Formulating and pronouncing the target language text

As far as the IT support offered by CASSIS is concerned - be it any of these sub-processes, which together lead to the creation of the target language production, **the interpreter will be assisted by the system in all the above-mentioned sub-processes:**

- the system allows the interpreter to read the speaker's speech in real time, thus avoiding the often time-consuming task of taking notes (interpreters typically take notes of numbers in speech during simultaneous interpreting, as this is the only way to accurately recall larger numbers in real time)
- thanks to the support, the tracking distance can be adjusted too, i.e. it can be made more comfortable (NB: too long a tracking distance puts unnecessary strain on the interpreter's memory; a short tracking distance increases the error rate due to structural differences between languages, and requires constant reformulation by the interpreter (see inflective and agglutinating languages, suffixation, conjugation, etc.), and the written version of the speech can reduce possible delays
- **the system greatly relieves the interpreter's memory, perhaps the most important argument in favour of CASSIS**
- the simultaneous presentation of the text gives the interpreter a sense of security and can even have a positive impact on his/her interpreting strategy, as well as greatly reducing the stress burden on him/her

- to complement all this, the interpreter is assisted by extensive databases linked to the system to identify target language terms. The system does this by visualising databases available on the Internet or prepared and pre-loaded by the interpreter. CASSIS highlights the formal information (visualisation), thus further relieving the interpreter's memory. This support also significantly reduces the burden on the interpreter on this side, thus significantly reducing the stress that can lead to performance degradation. By eliminating uncertainties (numbers, misinterpretation, backlogs), the psychological and physical burden on the interpreter is reduced, thus improving his/her reaction time, performance and the quality of the interpretation he/she provides.

The elements represented by CASSIS (written version of speech, terminology used in speech) thus provide the professional with visual input regarding

- a) the elements of speech which may be necessary to refer back to as a result of the *décalage* or even later (years, personal names)
- b) terms and their target language equivalents (source and target language pairs) which, according to experience, take much longer to search in the interpreter's mental lexicon, i.e. in the brain, than to read them off a screen

As described above, simultaneous interpreting is a very complex process, which means that the interpreter performs several operations at the same time. If, in addition, he is given an extra screen to look at at the same time, this could, in principle, create additional workload, forcing him to divide his attention further. The interpreter may miss the real-time comprehension of the source text by studying the information provided by the machine. It may seem that the technical

equipment does not help but rather hinders the work. In our research, we are therefore looking for ways to measure the extent to which computer support strains the interpreter's concentration. Tests so far have shown that adequate use of the support helps the interpreter's work.

It is worth noting that the rapid expansion and success of distance interpreting is proof of the wide spread of interpreters' attention.

We propose the following modifications to the Gile model (Gile 1999) in the application of CASSIS, based on the tests carried out during and before our research:

As a reminder:

$$SI = L + P + M + C$$

In other words, simultaneous interpreting (SI) is the result of the combined application of energy invested in the listening (L), parsing (P), memory (M) and coordination (C) elements of speech.

We say that the interpreter has to pay attention not only to the text of the speech but also to the different parts of the CASSIS display screen (SC=Screen) (T= recognized Text) and the word count (TB= Term Base Hits), each unit using different energy and all of which is beyond his/her mental capacity (K).

Thus the CASSIS version of the Gile model looks like this

$$SI = aL + bSC + cP + dM + eC < K$$

Where the lower case multipliers are the distribution of the total energy (E) consumed during the activity of the Interpreter over a given time period, by type: $E=1=a+b+c+d+e$ The distribution of the coefficients depends on the situation, and the interpreter's volitional and instinctive decision. The aim is to achieve a good distribution of the coefficients from person to person.

Where:

"E" is the absolute value of the total energy devoted to the different elements of attention,

"K" is the momentary available capacity of the interpreter, which he or she can regenerate to some extent during the rest period.

In other words, the interpreter needs to develop a strategy for his or her work that does not exhaust his or her mental capacity. Therefore, "E" should always be much lower than the "K" performance that can be activated.

And we not only assume, but have seen, that the apparent extra energy (effort) pays off, because the same or better interpreting performance is overall less tiring, less energy-consuming than the traditional method.

As can be seen from the literature reviewed in preparation for our topic, a growing number of researchers in the Far East - Iida et al. (1996)⁶, Itoh et al. (1997)⁷, Mima et al. (1998 - 7)⁸, Zong et al. (2002)⁹, Umeda et al. (2003)¹⁰, Xu & Sharoff (2014 - 8)¹¹, Wang et al. (2016)¹² - have addressed or are addressing the relationship between computers and interpreting. The results of speech processing are present in all of these systems, but in their research they are more integrated into dialogue systems rather than interpreting contexts. For example, the work of Jordan Boyd-Graber et al. (2016)¹³ points in the direction of machine interpreting, who looked

⁶ Hitoshi, Iida, Eiichiro, Sumita, Osamu, Furuse, *Spoken-Language Translation Method Using Examples*, *Proceedings of the 16th International Conference on Computational Linguistics*, 1996, Vol. 1, pp. 1074-1077.

⁷ Toshihiko, Itoh, Akihiro, Denda, Satoru, Kogure, Seiichi, Nakagawa, *A Robust Dialogue System with Spontaneous Speech Understanding and Cooperative Response*, *Proceedings of the Interactive Spoken Dialog Systems: Bringing Speech and NLP Together in Real Applications*, 1997, pp. 57-60.

⁸ Hideki, Mima, Hitoshi, Iida, Osamu, Furuse, *Simultaneous Interpretation Utilizing Example-based Incremental Transfer*, *Proceedings of the 36th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics and 17th International Conference on Computational Linguistics, Vol. 2*, 1998, pp. 855-861.

⁹ Chengqing, Zong, Bo Xu, Taiyi Huang, *Interactive Chinese-to-English Speech Translation Based on Dialogue Management*, *Proceedings of the Workshop on Speech-to-Speech Translation: Algorithms and Systems*, 2002, pp. 61-68

¹⁰ Masamitsu, Umeda, Satoru, Kogure, Seiichi, Nakagawa, *Interpreter for Highly Portable Spoken Dialogue System*, *Proceedings of the Fourth SIGdial Workshop of Discourse and Dialogue*, 2003

¹¹ Ran, Xu, Serge, Sharoff, *Evaluating Term Extraction Methods for Interpreters*, *Proceedings of the 4th International Workshop on Computational Terminology*, 2014, pp. 86-93

¹² Xiaolin, Wang, Andrew, Finch, Masao, Utiyama, Eiichiro, Sumita, *A Prototype Automatic Simultaneous Interpretation System*, *Proceedings of COLING 2016, the 26th International Conference on Computational Linguistics: System Demonstrations*, 2016, pp. 30-34.

¹³ Hey, Jordan Boyd-Graber, Hal Daumé III, *Interpretese vs. Translate: The Uniqueness of Human Strategies in Simultaneous Interpretation*, *Proceedings of NAACL-HLT 2016*, 2016, pp. 971-976.

at human strategies that can be recognized during interpreting and concluded that these methods are not easily implemented by machines. Some of the cited papers, on the other hand, specifically look for automatic solutions for interpreting. An example is the research by Mima⁸ et al. It is important to stress, however, that the aim of our research is primarily to support the interpreter, not to replace him or her, whether successfully or not.

Along the same lines, EU-BRIDGE, a project funded by EU R&D grants, was launched to develop a machine interpreting tool for the European Parliament [<http://www.eu-bridge.eu/communication.html>]. Although EU-BRIDGE is a much more ambitious project than CASSIS, the two ideas are certainly related in some aspects. For example, the issues of unknown terminology and the identification of pronouns in speech are definitely related topics in the two projects. This sub-project in the scope of EU-BRIDGE was the work of Alex Waibel's team, which achieved great market success (and is also known for the development of Jibbigo, acquired by Facebook): cf. Hamon et al (2009)¹⁴ , Spencer (2013)¹⁵ .

It is also important to point out that, in recent years, machine terminology extraction has also come to the fore in the context of interpreting: the paper by Xu and Sharoff (see 8) is an evaluation of methods for this purpose. We propose to include this method once the prototype is ready.

¹⁴ Olivier, Hamon, Christian, Fügen, Djamel, Mostefa, Victoria, Arranz, Muntsin, Kolss, Alex, Waibel, Khalid, Choukri, *End-to-End Evaluation in Simultaneous Translation. Proceedings of the 12th Conference of the European Chapter of the ACL*, 2009, pp. 345-353.

¹⁵ Malia, Spencer, *Facebook Acquires Pittsburgh Tech Firm. Pittsburgh Business Times*, Aug 13, 2013.

The present research does not aim at fully automated machine interpreting in parallel with automatic machine translation (MT), as our basic goal is to assist the interpreter in real time and support his/her preparatory work, not to replace it with a machine. Furthermore, as mentioned above, there are some events in conference interpreting that cannot be algorithmised and therefore cannot be automated, and important information for both the interpreter and the listener would be lost.

4. CASSIS AND MACHINE-ASSISTED INTERPRETATION

Machine interpreting is based on the speech-to-text - neural machine translation - text-to-speech process, using artificial intelligence support. In other words, word-by-word machine translation becomes speech in the target language, in machine voice.

The influencing factors of SI (simultaneous interpreting) have clearly shown that literal translation is not acceptable, i.e. the processing of linguistic culture, body language and what is seen in the room requires human beings until they can be solved *by neural networks*. Although the latter is also used by CASSIS, but in a different domain.

As far as research in Hungary is concerned, there is not yet much reference to the presence of machines in interpreting in the growing Hungarian-language literature. The book by G. Láng (2002)¹⁶ also focuses more on the teaching of interpreting and, by implication, on the qualitative issues of human interpreting. Szabari (1999) has a chapter on the evaluation of interpreting, but only discusses the difficulty of

¹⁶ Zsuzsa, G. Láng, *Tolmácsolás felsőfokon: a hivatásos tolmácsok képzéséről (Interpreting at the top: training professional interpreters)*, Budapest, Scholastica, 2002

measuring it, as it is mostly a subjective issue. Previously, for example, Pöchhacker (1994¹⁷) has discussed similar issues for languages other than Hungarian.

The use of infocommunication for interpreters, other than CASSIS but not in an integrated form, has been the subject of books published in the last few years and of several doctoral dissertations and academic theses.

The use of the computer is first mentioned in the Hungarian language in Horváth's 2012¹⁸ study. It mainly states that the computer is useful for terminological and content pre-processing for interpreters, in connection with which it refers to Sandrelli & De Manuel Jerez (2007)¹⁹. In the years since then, more and more tools based on corpus linguistic considerations have been published: see Pérez (2018)²⁰. Horváth also points out that it is not uncommon nowadays for "interpreters to work in front of their computers, so they have access to pre-written conversation samples in real time". What our project is attempting to do, however, is much simpler than the method described above.

Introducing the concept of *Computer-Aided Interpretation*, perhaps it is Kelly (2009²¹ - 12) who best captures what we are trying to do in our project. In his

¹⁷ Franz, Pöchhacker, *Quality Assurance in Simultaneous Interpreting*, in Dollerup, C., Lindegaard, A. (eds.) *Teaching Translating And Interpreting 2 (Insights, Aims, Visions)*, Amsterdam/Philadelphia: John Benjamins, 1994, pp. 232-242.

¹⁸ Ildikó, Horváth, *A fordító- és tolmácsképzés új kihívásai (The new challenges of translator and interpreter training)* In. Kinga, Klaudy (ed.) *Fordítás és tolmácsolás a harmadik évezred elején (Translation and Interpreting at the Dawn of the Third Millennium)*, ELTE Eötvös Kiadó, Budapest, 2012, pp. 152-155.

¹⁹ Annalisa, Sandrelli, Jesús, De Manuel Jerez, *The Impact of Information And Communication Technology on Interpreter Training: State-of-the-art And Future Prospects, The Interpreter And Translator Trainer* Vol. 1. No. 2., 2007, pp. 269-303.

²⁰ Pablo, Salvador Pérez, *The use of a corpus management tool for the preparation of interpreting assignments: a case study. Translation & Interpreting* Vol. 10, No. 1., 2018, pp. 137-151.

²¹ N., Kelly, *Moving Toward Machine Interpretation. tcworld January/February 2009*, pp. 15-17.

research, this author considers the following elements to be important to effectively present:

- the results of speech recognition
- text unit identification
- assigning thematic glossaries to text
- the connection of terminology databases
- and the efficient display of pre-translated schematic text units.

These are the elements that the author considers to be technologically mature enough to increase the efficiency of interpretation.

Finally, another Hungarian article on the subject is a study by Móricz (2016)²² , which deals specifically with the use of technical equipment by Hungarian interpreters. Móricz almost specifies how an interpreter support system should be built by integrating software technology tools used by interpreters (we consulted while during the time the PhD was written). To create all this, it is necessary to combine procedures that measure the efficiency of interpreting with the latest (even neural) technologies.

²² András Kristóf, Móricz, *Információ- és kommunikációtechnológiai eszközök használata a tolmácsolásban (The use of information and communication technology tools in interpreting)*. *Fordítástudomány* Vol. 18. No. 1., 2016, pp. 50-63.

5. THE TECHNOLOGICAL AND IT BACKGROUND OF CASSIS

History

In this section, we will review technological advances and recently released applications that can be used to support the interpreting process in a technological sense.

Let's start with translation: it is important to note that we believe that the translation of content on the internet, websites, blogs, and social networks is developing at the speed we are seeing today because the information technology of 2018-2019 is able to break through language barriers. Google is, of course, leading the way in this effort. There are countless applications, here are just a few:

<https://translate.google.com/>;

<https://9to5google.com/2017/07/18/google-analytics-adds-natural-language-search-machine-learning-based-tools-to-highlight-data/>;

<https://cloud.google.com/speech-to-text/> etc.).

In addition, a number of international companies (Amazon, Microsoft, Memsource, TAUS, DeepL ...) have developed services for NMT.

CASSIS also uses the potential of these techniques. In our country, this category previously included, for example, Morphologic's English-Hungarian machine translation experiments²³, and the so-called "smart glasses" (<http://glaces.com/mission/>), a sign language interpreter for the hearing impaired developed by Glaces.com Ltd., which interprets the speaker's words, displays them in writing and converts them virtually into sign language.

²³ It should be noted that Morphologic's initiative, launched in 1991, has been made obsolete in time.

Another example that can be mentioned is the SignAll sign interpretation system developed in Hungary (Zsolt Robotka 2022).

In the field of interpreting, up to now, computer technology has primarily enabled interpreters to search for specialist information/references while working, mainly via laptop, tablet or internet. In addition, of course, they have a wealth of material available on the Internet during their preparation; translation support tools enable them to translate written material provided in advance and thus prepare a terminological extract of the material in preparation for the interpreting assignment. However, a difficulty in this area is and has been the fact that the fundamental attitude of interpreters towards technical tools has remained negative (Pym 2011²⁴ , Z. Papp 2016²⁵ - comments by Lili Sotkovszky 2017). Papp and Sotkovszky have specifically contributed to the foundations of Cassis. The scepticism of interpreters and their resistance to technical advances have had the logical impact that, until today, the academic community has not sought to research and develop technical tools to assist interpreting (Fantinuoli 2018²⁶). Nevertheless, the practical application of Cassis has yielded positive results (see **our RESULTS** chapter and several theses on Cassis (Zoltán Papp, Lili Sotkovszky, Dániel Vígh, Ádám Gyarmati, in progress Benjamin Szilas Universität Wien as of 2012)

As far as CASSIS is concerned, using Fantinuoli's (2018² 153-174) classifications, our system is a "*process-oriented*" technology service: it aims to assist the interpreter in the sub-processes of interpreting. At the same time, it is also partly a "*setting-*

²⁴ A., Pym, *What Technology does to Translating. Translation & Interpreting.org*, 2011 (<http://www.trans-int.org/index.php/transint/article/view/121/81>, last consulted August 2018)

²⁵ Zoltán, Papp, *A tolmácsolás technológiai eszközökkel történő támogatása (Supporting interpretation with technological tools)*. Thesis, Budapest, 2016, BME

²⁶ C., Fantinuoli, *Computer-assisted interpretation: challenges and future perspectives. In Durán Muñoz, I. and Corpas Pastor, G. (eds.) Trends in e-tools and resources for translators and interpreters*, 2018, p.155.

oriented" technology, given that it influences the external circumstances of the interpreting process by the windows it displays. Existing process-oriented tools almost invariably support preparation prior to interpreting or assist in terminology retrieval during interpreting (Costa et al. 2014²⁷ , Costa et al. 2017²⁸). Our system goes beyond this: it provides simultaneous assistance to the interpreter during interpreting, without requiring more manual or intensive computer use by the interpreter.

Throughout our research, we have naturally monitored developments in the areas we deemed necessary and incorporated the results into our system at the appropriate stage of development. A central element of our project is the integration of existing performance and quality improvement applications into CASSIS. **The systems incorporated, their current state of development and their potential applications are described below.**

- Big Data

Big Data is a *large data set* that can help users understand certain processes, trends or make certain decisions in a structured or unstructured way. The initial methods of data collection have evolved considerably, with the volume of data being stored constantly increasing, and the fact that technology can keep pace with this and indeed store ever larger volumes of data. The amount of digital data that is the

²⁷ H., Costa, G., Corpas Pastor and I., Durán-Muñoz, *A Comparative User Evaluation of Terminology Management Tools for Interpreters*. In *Proceedings of the Workshop on Computational Terminology (CompuTerm '14), 25th International Conference on Computational Linguistics (COLING `14)*, 2014.

²⁸ H., Costa, G., Corpas Pastor, and I., Durán-Muñoz, *Assessing Terminology Management Systems for Interpreters*. In I., Durán-Muñoz G., and G., Corpas Pastor (eds.) *Trends in e-tools and resources for translators and interpreters*, 2017, pp. 57-84.

basis of today's research is now growing at an enormous rate. The Cisco [Visual Networking Index \(VNI\)](#) predicts that by 2022, data traffic will be higher than in the 32 years since the internet was first launched. Another major improvement is in the speed at which data can be processed, with technology capable of processing millions of data sets in tenths or even hundredths of a second. While this speed can be matched by the human brain in some respects (e.g. we can search our memories or frequently used foreign terms etc. with a speed that is difficult to measure), the human brain cannot comprehend and structure data of a similar nature at the same systemic speed as a machine. Because of this feature, the advantages of Big Data systems can be combined with the capacity of the human brain.

In the data processing process, it is worth mentioning that there is an increasing variety of data that can be handled. From structured, numerical sets, to text, images and sound, to data flows across systems, almost everything can be handled using Big Data. Collecting data across disparate systems is a challenge, as data rarely comes from a single source. It is therefore important to 'harmonise' and 'cleanse' the different data so that they can be matched and compared. If this is omitted, our data can be lost or lead to false results.

In addition to the collection of Big Data, its use is also a big challenge, since in order to really benefit from data collection and get reliable results, it is essential to choose the right analysis and processing criteria.

Among other things, databases have also made machine *learning* possible. Some stages of lengthy programming can now be triggered by simply teaching the system the next step. Without Big Data, this would of course be unthinkable.

In the field of linguistics, the *parameters of the various "language models"* are set using, among other things, sample data (e.g. voice recordings, dialogues, etc.) and statistical data extracted from large databases (e.g. the probability of occurrence of phonemes, the probability of word succession, etc.). Some speech recognition systems are also equipped with learning capabilities, in order to provide the highest degree of system flexibility."

While the most efficient technological element of machine translation today is the neural network, it should be kept in mind that in the static systems of the past, translation was based on existing text bases, i.e. on a large set of parallel texts and monolingual corpora. These corpora are still used today for machine translation, since the neural network requires that the source text be translated at word level. Or, more precisely, to have the huge corpus needed for speech recognition. Often the same monolingual corpus is used for machine translation and speech recognition.

Big Data is also an important basis for speech-to-text technology, since only with a large data set can we be sure that the voice recognition system we use will be able to interpret the different registers, accents and speech styles. This data is essential for the initial learning process of software.

- Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Artificial intelligence refers to machine "behavioural" processes that are very similar to the behavioural patterns of living beings with natural intelligence. And the way to do this, as with humans, is a process of learning through examples, data

sets, generalisations and inferences. An important requirement is that the knowledge thus acquired should enable the AI to communicate spontaneously with its environment. Artificial intelligence therefore has several layers, but overall it has not yet reached the level of maturity of the human brain, which consists of 80 billion neurons.

- Speech recognition (speech to text)

Continuously learning intelligent systems have contributed greatly to the development of speech recognition. There are two types of speech recognition technology: the first is dictation-based application, where the machine learns the voice of a speaker (this is done after reading several pages of text). This type of system can also perform punctuation correctly, which is a key aid for the subsequent interpretation of written text. The other application works with an unlimited number of speakers, and the system can theoretically perform speech recognition regardless of accent, style or register. The learning processes based on artificial intelligence are much faster and the size of the sample sets (data sets) used is very large, as they have to cover a large number of variations. However, at its current state of development, this system is not able to handle and reproduce punctuation efficiently, which is a disadvantage for the operation of CASSIS, as it may lead to misinterpretation of the displayed text by the interpreter.

There are several methods of speech recognition, including acoustic or pattern recognition. In the latter, *"the parameters obtained after pre-processing are compared by sample matching with reference samples or models that are created and stored during training. The basic units of recognition can be individual speech sounds and their combinations (double sounds, triads, semi-syllables, syllables,*

words or even longer phrases). In English and many other languages, words are the most suitable basic units. In Hungarian, because of inflexion and suffixation, each word can have hundreds or even thousands of forms, so units smaller than words are usually chosen. Speech sounds depend not only on the sound before/after them, but also on the acoustic environment, the speaker's person, gender, social and regional affiliation, etc. (Werner 2019) This method is too slow for us.

However, acoustic and pattern matching can be combined with artificial intelligence. The reason is that AI converts speech into well-structured algorithms with high efficiency, while also being effective at key stages of speech recognition: recognising units of speech, continuously improving algorithms, and monitoring the correctness of the input (speech) (Alhawiti 2015).

- Information extraction

The aim of information retrieval is to extract a well-organised, easily understandable set of information from a semi-structured or unstructured, computer-interpretable document. In other words, to produce the information we are looking for from the mass of information. Computer-readable and interpretable documents can be not only written text, but also image, audio or video files.

One of these processing methods is based on rule-based regular expressions (regex). It is based on a standardised algorithm that incorporates the expression or some of its elements. Based on the algorithm, it searches the database for the corresponding information. Such a method is used by MemoQ.

Deep learning can be used for more complex and difficult tasks. The multi-model architectures used for deep learning, the multilayer neural networks, are now

capable of processing power as high as the much simpler supervised machine learning models trained to solve a single problem (Endre Kiss 2017).

In 2016-2017, Yann LeCun, a professor at New York University's Bell Laboratory, developed LeNet, which is the basis of the deep convolutional neural network providing the highest image and speech recognition accuracy today. Also at the same time, the theory of Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, one of the most efficient methods for deep learning-based natural language processing and time series modelling today, was created at a renowned artificial intelligence research laboratory in Switzerland. In 2016, a paper published in Science by Geoffrey E. Hinton, Professor Emeritus at the University of Toronto, demonstrated a more efficient method than ever for learning deep networks with multiple hidden layers. He is partly credited with the concept of deep learning itself, whereby deep learning systems are defined as a structured set of machine learning algorithms whose layers can efficiently model an arbitrary process by extracting higher-level abstractions from input data. In practice, deep learning typically means the learning of deep neural networks.

Achieving these results was conditional on a dramatic increase in computing power. Learning neural networks involves performing a large number of matrix operations, similar to computer graphics. Since Graphical Processing Units (GPUs) optimised specifically for such operations have been used for the last decades, their application in deep learning was a given. Today's GPUs are evolving at a tremendous pace.

- Natural Language Processing (NLP)

Automatic language processing is a multidisciplinary field that includes linguistics, computer science and artificial intelligence. It is used in areas where it is important to integrate human language into machines. In the early days of the technology, it was based on grammar and statistics, but from the 1990s machine learning algorithms took the lead, and today NLP is increasingly being conflated with artificial intelligence.

Of course, the basics of grammar are still an important part of NLP technology, since the first step is always the lexical analysis, which extracts the elements of a text or group of words and "labels" them according to their grammatical classification (noun, verb, adjective, etc.). This is followed by a syntactic analysis to understand the sentence structure, and then a semantic and pragmatic analysis to interpret the words.

"The use of natural language as a communication tool is a way of serving human needs, but it also places a heavy burden on the machine. In particular, the input side, the use of human language as input, is difficult because of the diversity of the language spoken and the multiple levels of meaning carried. While processing language would require understanding of language, speech generation is a parameterised one-way process.

Understanding natural language is difficult for machines - and often for humans - because it requires a thorough background knowledge of the subject matter of the speech, and an understanding of the intended meanings behind the simple meanings of words. We know since the Turing test that the use of natural language is the criterion for true machine intelligence (Dudás 2011)."

The best known uses of NLP technology are in machine translation and assistants for large search engines such as Siri, Bing, machine translation, and aircraft maintenance .

- Part-of-speech tagging (POS tagging) (Kashefi 2018)

An important step in NLP technology, mentioned earlier, is "tagging", i.e. the classification of words into grammatical categories. The history of POS tagging is closely linked to corpus linguistics, where the first need to include the grammatical categorisation of words in the interpretation of a large set of words was first identified. The number of words that can be classified into several categories is language-dependent, and in Hungarian there are many such words (e.g. *spleen*, which denotes an organ as a noun, but can also be used as a verb). This is a matter for semantic and pragmatic analysis, involving the context.

For the CASSIS project, POS tagging is a very important technology, as the words in the glossary built by the interpreters have to be recognised by the machine and displayed on the screen in a certain way. If this is not done, entire keywords can be lost during the interpretation process.

But it is not enough to recognise these words: POS tagging technology must also be used to match them with the words in the glossary, even if they are in their conjugated form or plural. The proper nouns that are recognised are, fortunately, capitalised by the system, which is also important information for the interpreter, since, as already mentioned, the interpretation of proper nouns is a particularly difficult task in simultaneous interpreting. Identifying and displaying numerals and serial names as numbers is also a great advantage, especially in the case of numbers consisting of 4, 5 or even more elements (e.g. years, sums, statistics).

- University lecture translation system. The Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) has many foreign students. Therefore, as a result of about 10 years of research, a real-time text translation framework has been set up to break down language barriers. The basis of the system is partly similar to CASSIS, in that it integrates automatic speech recognition (ASR) and segmentation via Google applications in the cloud. It also uses neural machine translation (AI and Big Data applications in the background), one-shot learning algorithms to easily add new terminology to a topic.

6. PROPOSALS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF CASSIS USING INFOCOMMUNICATION TOOLS

At the start of the research, a trial version of the interpreter assistance system was already available.

There is a web-based system with a simple user-friendly interface, operating in its state prior to 09.08.2022.

- It takes advantage of Google Chrome web browser. The development is done through Firebase Console and CASSIS is hosted on this console in the cloud
- Text recognition is powered by the [Cloud Speech](#) API development platform, which integrates the search giant's highly advanced machine learning and [Cloud Machine Learning](#) application alongside the Cloud Platform IaaS and PaaS components.
- It uses Memoq as a search engine based on translation tasks to analyse the recognised text and display the relevant terms based on the glossary prepared by the interpreters, querying the prepared Memoq terminology

databases and comma-separated compressed data files (.csv). The function requires integration of the MemoQ API. Using Memoq's terminology database search system is much more efficient than .csv data. The so-called TB files are added to the system on a project basis. The access password gives the right to use only to the authorised interpreters, and with a time limit. After logging in, the connection between CASSIS and Memoq is established, the TB database elements for the project are displayed, and we can select which ones CASSIS should use for the interpreting work. The results for each file are displayed in a colour-coded list.

- all this requires a login to the version of memoq running on the server, which can be stored;
- The CASSIS interface contains the settings needed to customise the operation: source language selection, font size, line spacing, connection to the memoq server. The interface also shows the sound quality and the microphone enable for the speaker.

Next steps in research development:

- Logging in in person using Google/Facebook/Twitter/email to start working with CASSIS. CASSIS can only be used after login. This method will allow for the saving of configuration data in the cloud. And regardless of computer, the same CASSIS settings will be displayed based on the login profile.
- Browser-independent access to the web interface with the UX philosophy of not forbidding but allowing the user to "look around", facilitating the transition from the presentation version to the one the user needs.

- Saving selected TermBases to the cloud. The TB manager provider should be optional.
- Optional speech recognizers.
- Switching the language of recognition between source and target languages during work. If you switch languages, recognition will resume immediately in the other language. At the same time, the TB search direction is reversed too.
- Automatic sending of operational errors to for analysis.
- Reduce the response time for speech recognition and TB selection and search
- Create an install-only, cloud-independent system to prevent sensitive data from "leaking".
- Measuring memory usage.
- Dark design. With a switch on the toolbar, the surface changes colour according to the intended colour scheme to make working in a dark room more comfortable.

- Notes function. Double-clicking on a word in the recognised text window will copy it to the notes window. In the case of a phrase that consisting of several words that is recognised already, the whole phrase will be copied to the notes window. The notes remain freely editable.
- The development of the Speech to Text API automatically improves the efficiency of CASSIS, providing the following benefits:
 - Recognition will be more reliable
 - Mobile and tablet browsers can be supported
 - Automatic language detection between the selected 2-4 languages
 - Automatic punctuation, segmentation

- Recognising the speaker in dialogue. Recognised text can be separated and coloured per speaker
- Recognised words can be timestamped, so that the line break function can work more reliably by recognising significantly smaller pauses
- The speech recognition algorithm can also be given custom, context-dependent phrases in addition to its built-in dictionary, so it can recognise profession-specific phrases, which is not currently the case.
- Cooperative interpreting (Master / Slave). Cooperative method. Simultaneous interpreting is a two-way job. The feature allows two machines of two interpreters to communicate with each other while working. That is, the interpreters can see the same interface at the same time, but can also send messages and assistance to each other.
- In the case of training and certification, recording the voice of the interpreter(s), synchronising the two speeches.

7. THE PROCESS OF TESTING CASSIS

As mentioned above, a key element of our project was the testing process. The testing was carried out with 3 heterogeneous groups of interpreters: novice interpreters, already practising interpreters, experienced/professional interpreters. In addition, the testing environment can be further divided into three groups: we tested CASSIS in a live interpreting event, in a blind booth/silent-booth interpreting practice (live event, but with an interpreter booth with sound in, while

the interpreter is not connected to the room) and in a testing environment (simulation).

Before presenting the results of the questionnaire used in the testing exercise, let us turn to the evaluation aspects of interpreting as a language mediation activity. These are essential in assessing the quality of the interpreting work using CASSIS based on the the quality of the product (target language text) produced using CASSIS. The evaluation criteria are independent of the interpreting situation.

CRITERIA FOR THE EVALUATION OF INTERPRETATION

The basic criteria for good quality interpreting include a very high level of linguistic competence, a high level of language cultivation, a thorough knowledge of terminology, clear, intelligible speech, well-structured sentences, a pleasant tone of voice, good memory, anticipation skills, good stress management techniques, etc. However, these criteria are highly subjective and difficult to assess using metrics or rating scales. This difficulty is compounded by the fact that interpreting performance varies considerably, depending on the time of day, the duration of the interpretation or the difficulty of the subject. Without knowing the circumstances, it is therefore very difficult to judge an interpreter's performance with an 'external ear'. Nevertheless, research on this subject has been going on for several decades, and to a greater extent since the 1990s. Prior to the 1980s, scientific research had focused exclusively on the mental processes of language mediation, so that the fact that the interpreter's *raison d'être* is the listener, the receiving party, was not taken into account, since it is at the level of the receiver that the success of the interpretation and the achievement of its purpose are determined. It was in recognition of this idea that the evaluation of interpreting

became important and the quality criteria of the interpreter's work came to the fore. Quality, in this case, is nothing more than a degree of perfection, a kind of relative measure that everyone achieves in a different way.

The first research approached the quality of interpretation from two directions. First, from the point of view of *input*: for example, low-quality incoming sound, background noise, stress. Secondly, from the point of view of output, where errors, omissions, corrections and the degree of *décalage* were monitored. These aspects therefore show how subjective this area of research can be. *First of all, what do we call an error? Is it an error if an interpreter says 'arm' instead of 'forearm'?* (At a medical conference it certainly is, but when interpreting a humorous anecdote it may be a completely irrelevant detail.)

Or what is considered excessive *décalage*? There are interpreters with excellent short-term memories who can perfectly reproduce the spoken text with a delay of up to 20-30 seconds. Others "stick" closely to the source language, yet their production is coherent, the speech they formulate in the target language is precise and contains all the relevant information. There are, of course, cases which can be clearly diagnosed as errors, such as misinterpretation of factual information (numbers, proper names), or a level of discrepancy with the source text where it is clear that important information is being omitted or forgotten because of too great a time lag.

Stress is another factor that must be taken into account when interpreting. The question arises as to whether quality control should be carried out under the least stressful conditions possible in order to achieve an optimal, comparable result, or, on the contrary, should we create a situation that is more realistic, i.e. not too stressful, but still somewhat stressful? The second option may seem logical,

since no research is intended to analyse an artificial situation, but let us not forget *Dornic's* research²⁹ which showed that stress upsets the balance of bilingual systems, so that the stronger language will dominate. (By bilingual system, we obviously mean the brain in this case.)

As research in the 1990s found, the quality of interpretation can be greatly improved if the interpreter has a good view of the speaker. If the speaker reads his or her text, the importance of visibility is negligible, but a gesticulating performer who uses the space (stage) well is easier to interpret if, as an interpreter, we can see his or her movements. Generally speaking, visual input increases the interpreter's sense of security when working through what is essentially an auditory channel.

Another important factor that can also have a major impact on the quality of the interpretation is the pace of the speaker. The faster the source text, the more information is missed and/or misinterpreted. According to a study by Schiavon³⁰, a 1983 study found that a text densely enriched with numbers and proper nouns, when interpreted from English into Italian, is optimally interpreted at 100-120 words per minute. Any faster or significantly slower than this can clearly be at the expense of quality. The speaker's pace will of course be added to the differences in rhythm between languages.

The Moser-Mercer study was the first to identify 6 assessment criteria used in interpreter training:

²⁹ S., Dornic, "*The bilingual's performance: language dominance, stress and individual differences*", in *Language Interpretation and Communication*. ed. By D., Genver, & H.W., Sinaiko, New York, Plenum Press, 1978, pp. 259-270.

³⁰ V. Boschian Schiavon, *Velocità de parola e interpretazione simultaneal*, SSLMIT, Serie Monografie, N. 20, triste, Università degli Studi di Trieste, 1983

- Knowledge of native language
- Pronunciation, articulation
- Stress tolerance
- Confidence (assertiveness)
- Resilience
- Handling of technical equipment

Hildegund Bühler (1986) identified 16 linguistic and non-linguistic criteria, the importance of which was assessed by 27 interpreters within the AIIC (*Association Internationale des Interprètes de Conférence*³¹).

These criteria are as follows, in order of importance:

1. Sense consistency with original
2. Logical cohesion
3. Correct terminology
4. Fluency of delivery
5. Correct grammar
6. Completeness
7. Native accent
8. Pleasant voice
9. Appropriate style
10. Thorough preparation
11. Good stamina
12. Calmness
13. Pleasant appearance

³¹ International Association of Conference Interpreters: <http://aiic-usa.com/> (conference interpreting refers to consecutive and simultaneous interpreting).

14. Reliability
15. Teamwork
16. Positive feedback from the audience

The order suggests that content is more important than form. In addition to the first two substantive criteria, "reliability" and "thorough preparation" were given high priority. According to Bühler, some aspects can only be judged by the end-user, i.e. the audience, while others can only be assessed indirectly. An overall picture of quality can only be obtained by comparing the interpreted text with the original.

As a continuation of the research, Bühler also gave the list of criteria to conference attendants who had listened to the interpreted text, who prioritised the list differently from the interpreters. It can be concluded that active and passive participants in the interpreting process judge and define *quality work* differently. Research conducted in subsequent years has also produced different results, depending on the composition and mother tongue of the listeners studied. For example, participants at a technical conference are much less "sensitive" to a pleasant tone of voice, intonation and the pace of interpretation than those attending a literary conference. Subsequent research has also shown that quality criteria rank differently for men and women. For the latter, correct grammar and language level are of paramount importance, while men tend to consider style and the choice of words more important.

Practice and Kahl.³² show that it would be simpler to divide the criteria into objective and subjective groups. The first group includes the elements defined by

³² P., Kahl, "Translation quality - how can we tell it's good enough", in *Translating and the Computer* 12. Ed. By C., Picken, London, Aslib, 1991, pp. 149-158.

grammatical rules, i.e. grammatical correctness and pronunciation. The second group includes style, fluency, terminology, and the correct use/transposition of cultural aspects into the other language

After Bühler's research, we had to wait nearly a decade and a half for the next similar survey. Chiaro and Nocella sent the questionnaire to 286 interpreters in 2004, but it is not clear whether these interpreters were AIIC members. Thus, some researchers are of the opinion that the results of the two surveys should not be compared. In addition, Chiaro and Nocella asked the survey participants to draw up two lists of criteria: one for the linguistic elements and one for the non-linguistic elements. The resulting ranking is therefore difficult to compare with Bühler's results, but it is certainly worth taking into account in further research and for the establishment of criteria sets, e.g. for examinations.

1. Sense consistency
2. Completeness
3. Logical cohesion
4. Fluency of delivery
5. Correct grammar
6. Correct terminology
7. Appropriate style
8. Pleasant voice
9. Native accent

The next large survey (Zwischenberger & Pöchhacker) in 2008 followed Bühler's concept for comparability. In addition to Bühler's linguistic criteria, the authors also

included sound quality, lively intonation and the harmony between the interpreter and the speaker in the questionnaire. 704 AIIC members were interviewed for the survey. The results, in order of importance, are as follows:

1. Sense consistency with original
2. Logical cohesion
3. Fluency of delivery
4. Correct terminology
5. Correct grammar
6. Completeness
7. Appropriate style
8. Lively intonation
9. Pleasant voice
10. Synchronicity
11. Native accent

While there are some differences in the respondents and the survey methodology between the three surveys mentioned above, there is a clear trend in the way in which the profession evaluates quality interpreting performance: there is a marked increase in the importance of content, and a much lower emphasis on "packaging" and form.

The basis for today's criteria is to be found in the elements of the evaluation system used by the European institutions, in particular the SCIC, the European Commission's interpretation service. This is the organisation which organises the accreditation exam, i.e. the entrance examination for interpreters from the EU

institutions. The scoring table used by the jury is not public, nor is the set of criteria used by accredited interpreters to assess each other at set intervals. However, the assessment criteria used by the institution to help candidates prepare for the examinations are public. The scoring system used for the examination is based on this. Its elements are as follows³³ :

1. Content

1.1. Completeness

1.2. Accuracy

1.3. Coherence/plausibility

Was the logic of the original speech clearly recognizable?

Was the message coherent?

Were the main ideas and the structure rendered?

Were there any significant omissions with an impact on the coherence of the speech?

Were there any important mistakes (“contresens”)?

Did the interpretation render the original ideas/information of the speech accurately?

Was the content conveyed in full?

Were there too many details missing?

Were there any misleading or redundant additions (“embroidery”)?

Overuse of redundant filler phrases?

2. Delivery/Form

³³ http://europa.eu/interpretation/doc/marking_criteria_fr.pdf

2.1. Quality of active language

2.2. Communication skills

Knowledge of target language (correct grammar, appropriate register, idiomatic expressions, vocabulary, interferences from the source language)?

Appropriate choice of register?

Terminology?

Diction (mumbling or clear enunciation)?

Accent (if applicable)?

Pace of delivery (fluent or staccato)?

Use of the voice (prosody)? Intonation?

Was the delivery professional? Was it agreeable to listen to and confident?

Fluency of the delivery (“déalage”)? No abrupt or lengthy hesitations)?

Stamina?

Microphone discipline?

3. Technique

3.1. Interpretation strategies

Literal rendition of speech or intelligent processing of content?

Use of interpretation strategies (paraphrasing, output monitoring, ability to condense information, “telescoping”)?

Ability to monitor output?

Finishing sentences?

Several interpreting training centres in Hungary (where interpreting is taught and exams are conducted at university level) have set up their own assessment system based on this criteria. Most institutions assess content, linguistic formulation and

style, delivery and interpreting technique, and then each aspect is usually weighted, with content, for example, accounting for at least 50%. The full evaluation system is not publicly available in the case of universities either, but is very similar in principle to the SCIC's guidelines. In schematising the evaluation of the interpretation product, 3 main criteria should be taken into account in any evaluation process:

1. form (presentation)
2. content (fidelity)
3. interpreting techniques

As mentioned above, the testing was carried out among 3 different groups: experienced interpreters, moderately experienced interpreters, and completely novice interpreters. It is important to refer back to Gile's model of effort, which thus captures in its sub-processes the fundamentally very complex process of interpreting, as already detailed above.

The skill acquisition and application strategies of novice interpreters and experienced interpreters who are in the process of final examinations in interpreting skills could be compared to learning to drive. As we all know, as novice drivers, we are completely preoccupied with operating the car, with the ultimate goal of driving the route without causing an accident. For most novice drivers, getting from point A to point B is a challenge. If they are asked to do other driving/car-related tasks while driving (roll down the window, turn on the radio, start the rear wiper lever or rear window heater), they will have a much harder time and may not succeed at first. However, the more they practise and the more they drive, the easier it will be for them to perform parallel actions while driving

(even actions that are not intrinsically linked to driving, e.g. talking on the phone, listening to music, drinking/drinking, etc.). And the skilled driver will also be able to use GPS systems that greatly assist in getting from point A to point B safely and efficiently while driving.

The exact same thing happens with interpreting (CASSIS can be compared to the GPS system itself): the novice interpreter does not feel the ground under his feet at first, so busy is he with understanding and producing speech. At first, he will only be able to understand the text, and reproduce it in some way. Later, with practice, he will get to a more advanced level, and will be able to pay much more attention to the output, to the content, to correct himself, or even have the capacity to use a polished choice of words, etc. After a while, he will have no problem taking notes while interpreting, or even doing other activities while interpreting, will be able to use the equipment reliably (changing channels at the interpreter's desk), search and consult his prepared vocabulary, drink, text, look at websites, do crosswords (although opinions on the latter are very divided in interpreting circles). Gile's model of effort also focuses on these complex processes and their gradual acquisition. CASSIS can be easily placed in this model because it can support even the novice interpreter in his work by breaking down the complex processes of interpreting into parts. The use of the tool naturally requires extra effort at first, but the more experience an interpreter has, the more fluent he will be in using CASSIS. And using CASSIS pays for itself. Our testing processes clearly pointed out these elements.

TESTING

At the end of the testing, we had the interpreters fill out the questionnaire below (the results presented below were given both in live and practice situations, by novice and experienced interpreters).

The questionnaire was designed to answer the following questions: what kind of work the interpreter does, e.g. how he/she prepares for an assignment and what kind of technique/technological assistance/support he/she uses while working; what factors/elements he/she finds particularly difficult in interpreting in general and in the speeches given in the context of the test; how often and how effectively he/she used CASSIS during the interpreting process; which built-in elements did he/she find useful/unhelpful; how he/she thinks about the shared attention needed in the interpreting process, how he/she reflects on the issue; whether he/she can imagine working with this type of support in all his/her live work one day, whether he/she considers it an improvement/real help; whether he/she would therefore recommend it to his colleagues. Other questions sought to gauge how aware the interpreter was of his/her work and how he/she reflected on it. The main aim of the test, however, was to assess the usefulness of CASSIS support from the point of view of practitioners in the field. After back-testing the results, it can be said that the testing has led to some very promising conclusions.

Questions in the questionnaire:

*Sex **

*Age * (under 30, 30-40, 40-50, over 50)*

*Professional experience * (junior, early career, experienced, absolute old hand)*

Where did you get your interpreting qualifications?

Did you learn simultaneous or consecutive interpreting? (simultaneous, consecutive, both)

*Language combination **

*Have you ever tested CASSIS? **

*How would you define in one sentence the divided attention needed for interpretation? **

*In your experience so far, how can shared attention be enhanced/improved? **

*How do you usually prepare for a job? **

*What aids do you usually use when interpreting? **

- *Laptop or other type of computer*
- *Smartphone*
- *Online dictionaries*
- *Your own glossary in Excel or other format*
- *Homemade sauce on paper*
- *Post-its*
- *CAT tools*
- *Other aids in addition to the above*

*How did you prepare for today's work? **

*How would you rate your level of preparedness for today's job? (1 very poor, 5 maximum) **

*How stressed were you before today's interpretation? (1- not at all, 5- very) **

*How would you rate the cooperation with your cabin mate? (1 very bad, 5 very good) **

*How was interpreting with CASSIS today (1, very bad, 3, neutral, 5, very good) **

*How manageable do you find the CASSIS interface? (1- Not at all, 5- Very) **

*How difficult did you find the texts to be interpreted? (Rate from 1 to 3, 1: very difficult, 2: moderately difficult, 3: easy) **

*Please mark the 5 elements that you find most difficult in simultaneous interpreting in general! **

- *Numbers*
- *Proper names*
- *Functions*
- *Abbreviations*
- *Idiomatic expressions*
- *Panels*
- *Puns*
- *Quotes*
- *Abstract, convoluted thoughts*
- *References requiring background knowledge*
- *Length, density, complexity of sentences/thoughts*
- *Text coherence (shift of the relationship between speaker and speech intention)*
- *Specialist terminology and its frequency*
- *Speech rhythm*
- *Volume/sound quality*
- *Speaker style/voice*
- *Basic differences in the structure of the source and target languages*
- *Accent of the speaker*
- *Interpreting genre*

- *Your lack of preparedness*
- *Matching of culture-specific or specialist concepts*
- *Length of sequence to be transmitted (test duration)*
- *CASSIS has further divided my attention*
- *Any other specific difficulties you may have had:*

*Mark the 5 elements that proved the most difficult for you during today's interpretation! **

- *Numbers*
- *Proper names*
- *Functions*
- *Abbreviations*
- *Idiomatic expressions*
- *Panels*
- *Puns*
- *Quotes*
- *Abstract, convoluted thoughts*
- *References requiring background knowledge*
- *Length, density, complexity of sentences/thoughts*
- *Text coherence (shift of the relationship between speaker and speech intention)*
- *Specialist terminology and its frequency*
- *Speech rhythm*
- *Volume/sound quality*
- *Speaker style/voice*
- *Basic differences in the structure of the source and target languages*

- *Accent of the speaker*
- *Interpreting genre*
- *Your lack of preparedness*
- *Matching of culture-specific or specialist concepts*
- *Length of segment to be transmitted (test duration)*
- *CASSIS has further divided my attention*
- *Other*

*One by one, consider whether CASSIS has helped you overcome the 5 obstacles you have identified, and if it has, to what extent? **

*On a scale of 1 to 5, please indicate how useful you found it to see the text being interpreted in real time thanks to CASSIS (1 not at all, 5 very much) **

*On a scale of 1 to 5, please indicate how useful you found the terminological help provided by CASSIS (1 not at all, 5 very useful) **

*Has CASSIS helped you with any backlogs? * (Yes, No, Partially)*

*Which function of CASSIS is the most useful for you? **

Other useful function

*What elements of CASSIS or the CASSIS interface did you NOT get on with? **

How often have you looked at the CASSIS interface? (Constantly, Often, Occasionally, Never)

*What do you see as the weaknesses of CASSIS? **

*Would you use CASSIS in live work? **

*Justify your answer! **

*Would you recommend CASSIS to others? **

*Justify your decision! **

*What other features would you find useful in the CASSIS interface? **

Comment (write down anything you weren't able to say above but would like to)

OUR RESULTS

The responses received are presented in the Appendix, in this section we will only focus on the results that should be highlighted and analysed with regard to CASSIS.

1. DIVIDED ATTENTION - Theoretical background: a single theoretical question was asked to the respondents and was also used to raise awareness in a practical sense. The question was how the interpreter would define the divided attention that is central to interpreting. Several of the novice interpreters and some of the moderately trained interpreters reported some kind of goal to be achieved when describing/defining divided attention. In their responses, they linked the concept to 'leap-frogging', 'fragile balance', 'doses of attention'. Gile's model of effort was clearly mirrored by the responses:

"Basically, it's like leap-frogging. The person crouching in front of us is the speaker, and we are trying to catch up, and it basically becomes a kind of round-and-round 'chase' between the interpreter, the speaker, and the text (target text and source text). Once we've caught up and leapt over it, it's in front of us again, and we try to leap over it again."

Respondents also mention that divided attention:

- is the cornerstone of simultaneous interpretation
- relies on the interpreter's working memory resources
- is based on the operation of individual parallel channels
- requires a high level of concentration and speed from the professional
- and also puts a considerable cognitive burden on him/her.

2. PRACTICING THE DIVISION OF ATTENTION

In a follow-up question, we naturally also asked how/why the interpreters felt that divided attention could be improved. The answers were quite varied, but most of them agreed that "a great deal of practice" is needed to develop this skill. In addition to responses such as

- eliminating distractions, improving concentration
- thorough preparation (knowledge of technical terms)
- rest,

respondents therefore encouraged developing automatisms in practice. Some answers which should be highlighted show that the practice in question is also imagined by the novice interpreters themselves as a breaking down of the complex basic process of interpreting into sub-processes:

"It can be improved through a lot of practice. For example, if you get used to speaking and listening at the same time. Once you have a steady pace that you have learned to manage consciously, you can try to do other things while you are speaking, like writing down a word/number or two or opening a website, or typing a word and seeing if you get out of the flow of interpreting or not."

Another respondent stressed the need for proper allocation of mental resources during simultaneous interpreting:

"Practice and the development of automatisms can contribute greatly to the interpreter's ability to use a greater proportion of mental resources for attention sharing, so I think these two factors play a big role in development."

Another opinion is that it is important to have the text before the interpretation:

"On the one hand, it is a matter of practice, and on the other hand, the interpreter must have the text to be interpreted at his or her disposal beforehand. CASSIS can be useful in this respect."

3. PREPARATION

With respect to the use of CASSIS, we also considered it important to ask how our interpreters prepare for each job. The questionnaire concerning preparation had 2 parts:

A, how an interpreter prepares for an interpreting assignment in general

B, how the interpreter has prepared for this particular assignment.

In our opinion, it is also important to address the issue of preparation because, although we believe that CASSIS is certainly NOT a substitute for preparation, it facilitates it to a large extent and, most importantly, as preparation for the assignment, it links the preparation material and the work by converting the glossary prepared by the interpreter and the terms contained in any material received in advance into a TB and entering them into the system.

The responses to the questions on preparation confirm this assumption.

A, Respondents generally prepare for interpretation assignments as follows:

- requesting the client to hand over the presentations/speeches prior to the interpreting event
- requesting the names of opponents/companies from the client
- requesting functions and positions from the client
- writing/noting these on a separate sheet/into a separate document, which can be used directly at the conference during work

- depending on the time, familiarising oneself with the speeches received, making notes, translating, sight-reading and preparing them
- preparing a list of terms, based on the speeches received, the detailed conference programme and any parallel texts found
- conceptual preparation (company website, concept conversions ...)
- reading about the topic
- getting acquainted with the technical vocabulary, learning words
- searching the internet for video or audio material for the speaker (this will greatly help the interpreter to prepare for the pace of speech, style of speaking and possible accent of the speaker)
- identification of video material about similar events available on the internet (previous year's event, etc.)

B, In addition to the above, respondents prepared for the job as follows:

- printing programme brochures in the target and source languages
- printing out the preparation material received, highlighting the technical terms and writing out the target language equivalents above/next to the term.

Two answers are worth highlighting: *"Not knowing the precise topics involved by the speeches, I tried to familiarise myself with the field and the technical terms and expressions from what I found relevant on the Internet, from which I then prepared a glossary manually."*

Also: *'orientation by programme points'.*

The answers on preparation clearly show the thorough work that goes into the assignment of interpreters. However, it also shows how interpreters can lose the ground from beneath their feet if they do not have any preparatory material at their disposal. It should be noted that this is very often the case. We do not have precise statistics on how often and why clients do not provide interpreters with any preparation material, but we will try to review cases which clearly confirm that the visual input and terminological support provided by CASSIS greatly reduces the cognitive load and stress on the interpreter, both during the preparation for the assignment and during the work.

The most common cases are:

- The interpreter simply does not receive any material because the client does not understand the connection that the more he or she contributes to the preparation of the language mediator, the better quality and more accurate the interpretation will be. It is therefore easy to see that this is ultimately not only in the interpreter's interest, but also in the direct interest of the client. It is completely unreasonable to write an overwhelming, highly technical, quote-laden or even funny presentation and expect the interpreter to deliver it with 100% accuracy without any preparation material. (Of course, some interpreters do overcome these obstacles, but this is more likely to happen if they arrive at the event prepared.) Interpreters' associations and advocacy bodies still have a lot of work to do in this respect, as it is important to make the client understand that the interpreter's preparation is an integral part of the interpretation of the presentation, and that it is directly proportional to

the quality of the interpretation provided at the event in terms of time, energy and quality. (Interpreters refer to this as 'client education' among themselves.)

- The interpreter receives the material the evening before the conference because it will only be ready by then. By that time, he or she does not have enough time to go through the itemised preparation process described above, and may not even have the time to become sufficiently familiar with the structure of the material. This also means that, even though the speaker has a pre-written version of the text, it is very often the case that the speaker spontaneously skips parts, makes additions, completely changes his speech, says something else, etc., and the interpreter cannot handle these extremely complex interpreting sub-processes in addition to reading. Last-minute materials are useful to enable the interpreter to roughly define for himself the professional depths to which the presentations described in the programme are intended to take the listener. Of course, this is extremely useful information from the perspective of the interpretation, but if, on the last night, it turns out that the interpreter's preparation is not satisfactory, the stress is much greater than if he or she is unaware of the discrepancy. In addition, it should never be forgotten that a fundamental condition of interpreting is that the interpreter is well rested, so he or she cannot be expected to spend the nights before the event with preparation (whether it is a multi-day or one-day event). The same applies to breaks during interpretation: simultaneous interpreters usually take turns every 20-25 minutes. This ensures the quality of interpretation throughout a day-long

event. If an interpreter who is taking a break has to spend it with studying the speech, he or she will not be able to rest and this will obviously have a negative impact on performance.

Last-second materials are given to the interpreter immediately before the conference. He or she may still have time to highlight a quote, look it up, identify numbers and names in the text, but this greatly increases the stress immediately before the work, which is understandably not very fortunate. The availability of the text may reduce stress somewhat if the interpreter, consulting the text, finds that he or she has prepared adequately even without it, but let's face it, this is much less common than the opposite. Furthermore, the availability of the text in this case does not allow the interpreter to become thoroughly familiar with its structure, so the speaker's spontaneous, last-minute, frequent changes will force him or her to concentrate on the text being read, rather than trying to find the part of the several-page, unfamiliar document where the speaker has just jumped to in the last few seconds. After a while, the interpreter will give up on the written version of the text because the feverish search for what is being said takes up his or her remaining resources. It should be remembered that, in the meantime, the interpreter is listening to the interpreter's text, who knows nothing about the difficulties the interpreter is experiencing and is therefore unable to help him or her in his or her predicament. It is generally believed that the interpreter 'should handle' the problem. It can be seen from the above that it is not the interpreter who has to do the preparation, but the organisers, the experts in the subject, who have to contribute to the cooperation between the two parties, as this is in the best interests of both. Similar cases are addressed in research on text-assisted simultaneous interpreting (e.g. Rohonyi 2018, Vígh 2019). Vígh's thesis also analysed the use of CASSIS in this situation.

The ideal situation would, of course, be for the interpreter to receive most of the text in advance, create terminology from it and feed it into the system, so that he or she can use it efficiently in the course of the work. (It is also often forgotten that the interpreter prepares for a complex event for as many days as the event/conference itself lasts: a 2-day conference can be preceded by 2 days of thorough preparation, since the interpreter not only has to memorise the words,

but also has to have a conceptual understanding of the subject in question in order to interpret intelligibly and reliably. It is important to note here that, while translators specialise in a specific field (law, marketing, etc.), interpreters interpret at conferences related to a variety of subjects/fields of specialty, which in turn implies the need to be familiar with the subject area in question by the time the conference starts.)

In summary, we can see that CASSIS can greatly facilitate the interpreter's preparation for the job in hand, and its use can also significantly reduce the burden on the interpreter and improve the quality of the interpretation.

4. WORK

After the section on preparation, the questionnaire included several questions on aspects of the actual work. These were ultimately aimed at finding out which parts of the process the interpreters value as help/support for the CASSIS system (it was also important to ask about factors that could influence the interpreter's performance during testing, both subjectively and objectively: how difficult they find the texts to be interpreted, how they cooperate with their interpreting partner, etc.).

4.1. AIDS

In the next group of questions, we asked about the technological/IT/other aids used by interpreters in their work. Our conviction that the integrated system of CASSIS also relieves the interpreter's workload in this respect during his/her work

and preparation was confirmed. The following tools appeared prominently in the responses (from top to bottom, from most to least frequently used):

- laptop, computer
- smartphone
- online dictionaries
- a self-made glossary in Excel or other CAT format
- post-it notes
- CAT tools
- notebook.

As described above, CASSIS can use all of these on a single computer and manage them together as part of an integrated system.

4.2. FACTORS CAUSING DIFFICULTIES IN SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETATION

The difficulties identified by the interpreters who took part in our testing coincide, by definition, with the elements already detailed in the chapter on interpreting. However, if you look at the list of difficulties, you will see that CASSIS can provide a very satisfactory answer to most of them. Of course, CASSIS cannot help to overcome interpreting difficulties arising from a lack of background knowledge (except for the immediate and continuous display of speech in written form), nor can it correct a bad speaker's stuttering, incoherent delivery, change his accent or the tone of his delivery, nor can it understand puns for the human interpreter, but it can be used very effectively to overcome certain difficulties in many other areas (numbers, functions, abbreviations, technical terms, etc.). The responses reflect this statistically:

Please mark the 5 elements that you find most difficult in simultaneous interpreting in general!

11 replies

4.3. DIFFICULTIES ENCOUNTERED IN THE COURSE OF A GIVEN ASSIGNMENT

Distribution of responses to the following question:

Mark the 5 elements that proved the most difficult for you during today's interpretation!

11 replies

5. EVALUATION OF CASSIS

5.1. USER INTERFACE

The majority of our interpreters who tested the CASSIS interface rated it as good.

How manageable do you find the Cassis interface? (1- Not at all, 5- Very)

11 replies

5.2. THE USABILITY OF CASSIS

We asked open questions regarding opinions on the use of CASSIS in a live situation.

From the answers, here are some thoughts worth reflecting on:

"The visualisation of the speaker's text, who had an an overly strong accent that sometimes bordered on the unintelligible, helped a lot."

"It's harder to navigate through tangled thoughts while also having to pay attention to extra things, but at the same time, if I don't catch anything, at least I have the text written down."

"I could look at the spoken text whenever I wanted, remembering numbers and proper names was not a problem, and it also helped me to understand what the incoherent speaker was saying".

In addition, CASSIS:

- wrote out the numbers extremely well
- personal names, proper nouns
- helped in textual contexts
- helped a lot in catching up.

In conclusion, it is clear from the answers given to the questions directly related to the usefulness of CASSIS that the use of the system is a great support in the face of the difficulties described in the chapters on the interpretation process:

A, First of all, it should be pointed out that the interpreters' feedback clearly indicates that the visual input provided by CASSIS is useful, as it has greatly reduced the psychological burden on them, among other benefits, of course.

B, CASSIS also helps one catch up:

Did Cassis help you catch up?

11 replies

C, The usefulness of the terminological assistance provided by CASSIS was also confirmed. The majority of interpreters clearly found this function very useful. Other functions are also useful according to the interpreters.

Which function of Cassis is the most useful for you?

11 replies

D, Other useful elements:

- simple interface
- distinguishing the sources of terminology matches by colour.

9. CONCLUSION - BACK-CHECK

In our research, we sought to answer the following questions:

1) Original research questions and hypotheses

- a. Does the planned computer solution improve the interpreter's psychological performance?
- b. Does the search for the appropriate target language terminology based on the source language provided by the interpretation support system help to better and more efficiently formulate the target language text, or does it slow down and make the cognitive management of the whole process more difficult?
- c. Does the immediate availability of target language versions of the terminology units increase the efficiency of the interpreting work?
- d. Can the display of the heard text really help the interpreter to make more economical use of his/her working memory and reduce the interpreter's psychological workload?
- e. How many elements of a long list did the interpreter manage to translate into the other language with and without the tool developed?
- f. Is there any justification for a comparative analysis of the products obtained with different parameter settings?

- g. With which configuration does the interpreter reproduce the source text more accurately, pragmatically and stylistically?
- h. Using the current version of the prototype to investigate how to increase interpreting efficiency, which of the changes would have a more effective impact?
- i. Which machine support is more or less demanding on the interpreter's attention?
- j. Can the interpreter's attention sharing be restructured compared to current models?
- k. What tools and procedures can be used to measure the interpreter's effectiveness?
- l. Can speech recognition reduce the use of so-called "temporary memory"?

2) How can tools in the field of infocommunication be integrated to complement the system design?

3) Developing tests and measurements and assisting in their evaluation. With the results achieved, we want to verify the prototype's usability and prove the usefulness of the product.

4) The production of the current version of the prototype justifies a specific model for the interpretation process. In order to further improve the efficiency of the product, a proposal for an improved model is sought by examining the CASSIS models and the literature.

Our research clearly confirmed the hypothesised answers to the questions posed.

10. THE PERSPECTIVES OF CASSIS

- When we started our research, we had the following ideas for the testing: *once the first version of the system was ready, it would be presented to a limited number of interpreters. After a short period of 2-3 suitable practice interpreting sessions, we would test its use in real life. By that time, the interpreters would have had the opportunity to familiarise themselves with the system, customising the windows and the display if necessary. After feedback from the interpreters and the results of the first measurements, the system would be improved as necessary and tested again as described above. We cannot quantify the quality of an interpreter's speech, but we can use comparative methods to assess it. Based on language teaching, client value judgements and other sources, we develop a virtual "Excellent Interpreter" with the most perfect qualities and skills imaginable, which we compare with the quality of the performance of the person who takes the test under different conditions. The lessons learned from this will also be utilised in shaping our model.*

As a continuation of our research, we intend to follow the guidelines described above. It remains important that the process of identification with CASSIS allows interpreters to tailor the interface to their own needs, thus further enhancing their sense of ownership of the support provided by CASSIS.

- We will continue to test the 3 heterogeneous groups identified: complete beginners, practising beginners, experienced interpreters (live assignments and simulations), but the details are still being worked out.

- As pointed out by Fantinioli (2018), a strong emphasis should be placed on testing, as well as EEG and eye movement tracking. We plan to use the latter ourselves in future measurements.

As a new element, we would like to test CASSIS in an educational environment in the future, as we believe that the learning of how to use the support can be done in parallel with the learning of interpreting techniques. We assume that a different use of CASSIS may characterise a novice interpreter who is learning to interpret with CASSIS to begin with.

The system can also be used in education outside the classroom in simulated conferences.

It is also possible to use CASSIS in an exam situation, but further research is needed.

Proposals for what should come next

Based on the evolution of infocommunications and trends, we propose the following:

- Strengthen the use of artificial intelligence and its frontier areas, for example by:
 - on-shot learning
 - automatic bilingual terminology search
 - incorporating specific terminologies into speech recognition
 - possibly integrating neural machine learning
 - better use of the cooperation of the current CAT tool by improving the quality of segmentation targeting
- Keeping up with the rapid development of information technology and linguistics to strengthen embedded services.
- Solve the problem of the independence of the CASSIS service from the cloud, from the built-in auxiliary engines.
- To find answers to the questions posed in the hypotheses that did not fit into the framework of a prototype project.

ANNEXES, APPENDICES

Annex 1

DEFINITIONS

anticipation	a basic interpreting strategy, which refers to the interpreter's attempt to guess how an open idea or sentence structure will be concluded.
API	application programming interface. The documentation of the procedures (services) of a program or system program and that may be used by other programs. A public API makes it possible to use the services of a program system without having to know its inner workings.
speech perception	A subfield of phonetics or psycholinguistics, in a narrow sense meaning the perception of speech, and in a broader sense speech comprehension. http://www.kislexikon.hu/beszedpercepcio
speech production	the process from the intention of speech to its pronunciation. Speech is preceded by both the planning of the idea intended for others and the assignment of the appropriate target language form. These two processes take place simultaneously, requiring divided attention
big data	is about processing large amounts of data, which change at a high speed and are very diverse.
sight-reading ('blatt')	"reading" a written text in the target language. Interpreting at the same time as reading
CAT (computer assisted translation)	computer-assisted translation system
target language	the language into which the interpretation is being provided

.csv	a file capable of storing data in columnar order, separated by a character. Can be opened in Excel or created from Excel.
décalage	the time difference between the result of the interpretation and the spoken speech, in seconds
Factual elements	Factual, i.e. interpreting mainly proper names, numbers, and quotations.
Firebase	A Google suite of services, which is a cloud-based mobile backend service (BaaS) that allows developers to focus only on client-side code
source language	the language of the speaker's speech. Interpreting is from the source language into the target language
effort model	Interpreting consumes limited mental energy. The number and amount of energy required for the various processes varies depending on the strategy, and this energy is consumed at varying rates over time.
cognitive	cognitive and thinking activities such as perception, attention, memory, counting, language use
consecutive interpretation	the interpreter is seated next to the speaker and performs so-called short or long-segment interpreting without the use of a booth. The interpreter therefore does not speak in parallel with the speaker, but interprets in segments of widely varying length, ranging from a 1-minute to a 10-minute speech. Consecutive interpreting is most often used when the presence of an interpreter is important (e.g. at protocol events, meetings, exhibition openings) or when an interpreting booth is not available. In comparison with simultaneous interpretation, an important aspect is that consecutive interpretation practically doubles the length of the event. In addition, since in consecutive interpreting the interpreter works from notes and memory, this genre is considered much less accurate than simultaneous interpreting.
external ear	an independent person to assess the interpreter and his/her work
deep learning	deep learning systems are a structured set of machine learning algorithms whose layers can efficiently model an

	arbitrary process by extracting higher level abstractions from input data
shared attention	comprehending and executing several events simultaneously. It depends on the interpreter's strategy as to what he or she focuses on. Can be practised and developed
MT machine translation	Machine translation. Neural machine translation (NMT) is its artificial intelligence-enhanced version of
Sensory, short-term, long-term, working memory	Storage methods for information processing. Types and location of memory in the brain for interpreting processes (Horváth 2015)
psycholinguistics	psychology of language, an interdisciplinary field: psychology, cognitive science , linguistics
simultaneous interpretation	a type/technique of interpreting used at monolingual or multilingual conferences, where the interpreter performs his/her task simultaneously, i.e. the interpreter "receives" the speech in the room - the so-called source text -, while sitting in an interpreter booth, into his/her earphones, and interprets it speaking into a microphone with a few seconds' delay into a language other than the original language (target language), which the audience also listens to through headphones, while also being able to hear the speaker.
interpretation with the assistance of a translator	Simultaneous interpretation of prepared and read text
Suprasegmentation	The suprasegmental structure is the aspect of the complex speech signal generated by the speech production process that can be described as process variations in time, frequency and intensity, and can only be perceived relative to each other. [Markó A. PhD thesis 2005]

technology	A set of procedures and methods (a systematic procedure, method, expertise) by which a goal can always be achieved, a product can be made, or a service can be provided with consistent success
terminology database	a collection of monolingual or multilingual terms. In this case, to assist translation and interpretation
term	interpretation of form (name) and substance (concept)
bionics,	a cross-disciplinary branch of science aiming to translate solutions developed in living nature into technical practice
infobionics	the application of informatics in the field of bionics
neurolinguistics	the science of neural mechanisms in the human brain. It investigates what controls the understanding, production and acquisition of language. It draws on methodologies and theories from fields such as neuroscience , linguistics , cognitive science , neurobiology, communication disorders, neuropsychology and computer science

QUESTIONNAIRE FOR TESTING:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSci_ajpuy1orkyUUEofO5mkG9wiTGE1GxhUY_ddqL_vFK7F5w/viewform

RESULTS

Aggregated responses to the questionnaire:

Your Gender

11 replies

Your age

11 replies

Your professional experience

11 replies

Where did you get your interpreting qualifications?

11 replies

BME

Pázmány Péter Catholic University

University of Vienna

ELTE

I am still a student.

BME, Université de Strasbourg

BME

Did you study simultaneous or consecutive interpreting?

10 replies

Your language combination (example: Hungarian A, French B, English C)

Have you ever tested CASSIS?

11 replies

How would you define in one sentence the divided attention needed for interpretation?

11 replies

Very important,

It's like the frog-leaping. The person standing/squatting in front of us is the speaker and we try to catch up and it becomes a round and round 'chase' basically. Once we catch up and jump over him, he's in front of us again and we try to jump over him again.

Divided attention is a fragile balance that comes from the correct allocation of "attention doses" to each area.

Highly concentrated attention, relying mainly on working memory resources.

Operation of parallelly connected channels

The interpreter is faced with significant cognitive load in the form of a visual input (the written version of the speaker's text) and audio input (the spoken speech).

Shared attention is the basis of simultaneous interpretation.

You talk while you listen, listen while you talk, interpret, switch, and pay attention to the difficult elements (numbers, names, etc.) and rhythm.

You need to simultaneously pay attention to many inputs that can only be partially prepared for, e.g. speaker, text, gestures, PPT, references, cultural phenomena, etc.

Sharing attention requires enormous concentration and the brain inevitably selects information, so some information is more easily lost during the interpreting process.

Speed of perception, interpretation and reaction

In your experience so far, how can shared attention be enhanced/improved?

11 replies

With practice and special games

With a lot of practice, if we get used to speaking and listening at the same time. Once you have a steady pace that you can manage, you can try to do other things while you are speaking, such as writing down a word or two that you have heard, or opening a website, or typing a word and seeing if you are getting out of the way.

It takes a lot of practice, and it makes things a lot worse when a new area comes in and takes a piece of your attention

Practice and the development of automatisms can greatly contribute to the interpreter's ability to use a greater proportion of mental resources for attention sharing, and I believe that these two factors play a major role in development.

improving concentration, eliminating distractions

It is a matter of practice on the one hand, and on the other hand, the interpreter must have the text in advance. The CASSIS interface can be useful for numbers and "risky" proper names.

Shared attention is improved if distracting noises can be excluded.

With thorough preparation and good support materials.

With practice, preparation, routine

Knowledge of the subject and terminology, relaxation.

Lots of practice in the field and off the job (listening to the radio and interpreting, etc.)

How do you usually prepare for a job?

11 replies

In depth

I ask the client for all presentations, speeches and the speakers' names, print them out and make notes of the technical terms. If time permits, I even translate the presentation by hand into hard copy. If background material has been provided, I will also process it and look up companies and speakers on the internet (own website, LinkedIn, etc.). I will also check if there is video or audio material of the speaker online (e.g. on YouTube), so I will know what will be expected of me (speaking pace, style, accent). In addition, I will check if there is video material of the event/conference from previous years online and if so, I will check for frequent speakers at home. I look through videos I find of speakers and/or the conference at home. If I can't find any, I watch a few relevant videos on the topic, make a note of them and scan them down. In the absence of video and audio material, I sight-read the background material I have received. I usually also write out the names and positions of people (in both languages) + names of institutions on a separate sheet of paper, which I always keep in front of me so that I can quickly glance at it while interpreting.

I read about the topic, using parallel texts and articles, based on which I can make my glossary. I like to spend at least half a day just with the finished glossary, maybe watching videos.

Familiarising myself with the background material on the topic, making a glossary of any terms or words that may be used, listening to existing speeches, listening to lectures on similar topics, trying to interpret them.

I prepare a TB, read a lot in both languages on the subject and watch videos of expected speakers

I'll make a glossary, read up on the topic of the event, and ask for the speakers' materials.

I learn words, sight-read existing texts, and read into the topic.

I immerse myself in the topic, read through the available materials and sample texts from the speech repository, watch related youtube videos

I try to collect the available material, look up the speakers, listen to their previous presentations if possible.

Setting up and learning a glossary, browsing general and specific information on a topic

What aids do you usually use when interpreting?

Other aids in addition to the above

1 answer

notebook

How did you prepare for today's work?

11 replies

In depth

I printed out the programme brochures (in English and Hungarian), wrote down the name of the moderator and the guest. Then I printed out the preparation materials, underlined the terms and wrote the translation above them. I found a half-hour talk about the work of one of the organisations, watched it I also looked at the websites of the Ministry of Education and the School of Public Life and collected some terms.

I read Tessza's material and watched a lot of videos about Barcelona en Comú and the theory of municipalism in general

On the one hand, I used the materials provided by the organizers, and on the other hand, in the absence of precise information on the topic of the lectures, I tried to get acquainted with the field and the technical terms and expressions from the materials I found relevant on the Internet, from which I then made a glossary.

glossary, orientation based on programme points

-

I looked at the material from the organisers and read up on the subject.

There was no preparation material.

I immerse myself in the topic, read through the available materials, sample texts from the speech repository, watch related youtube videos

By making a glossary

See above

How would you rate your preparedness for the job today? (1 very poor, 5 maximum)

11 replies

How stressed were you before today's interpretation? (1- Not at all, 5- very)

11 replies

How would you rate the cooperation with your cabin mate? (1 very bad, 5 very good)

11 replies

How was interpreting with Cassis today? (1, very bad, 3, neutral, 5, very good)

11 replies

How manageable do you find the Cassis interface? (1- Not at all, 5- Very)

11 replies

How difficult did you find the texts to be interpreted? (Rate from 1 to 3, 1: very difficult, 2: moderately difficult, 3: easy)

11 replies

Please mark the 5 elements that you find most difficult in simultaneous interpreting in general!

11 replies

Any other specific difficulties you may have

1 answer

Accent,

Mark the 5 elements that proved the most difficult for you during today's interpretation!

11 replies

One by one, consider how much Cassis helped/helped you to overcome the 5 obstacles you have identified

11 replies

I don't remember the obstacles.

it did not work

It spelled out the songs very well, the performer's accent didn't improve Cassis' performance (to say the least), but it definitely learned, it recognized more and more what was going on; background knowledge is not expected from Cassis, of course, and I know it can't be avoided, but it really hinders my concentration when something moves on the monitor (I also get distracted when I see my own mouth on the plexiglass, so I'm quite sensitive)

Unfortunately, I was unable to use Cassis during the test.

I could use numbers and textual context when I fell behind the speaker

1, displaying numbers on screen no longer requires extra cognitive effort, and that's good

2, though the proper nouns were not always accurate, if something close to the original name was shown, it helped at least in the phonetic pronunciation

3,

4, I was helped by the visualisation of the accent, which was too strong and sometimes almost unintelligible

5, chopped it into meaningful segments

It provides a lot of help with proper names and numbers.

It's harder to navigate through the tangled thoughts when you also have to pay attention to extra things, but at the same time, if I don't catch anything, at least I have the text. It spells out numbers well, but not so with names/abbreviations.

-
As I could always look at the text that had been spoken, remembering numbers and proper names was not a problem, or, if the speaker was not coherent, it helped me to understand what he was saying.

For numbers to a very large extent, and for proper names and functions as long as they were spelled it correctly

On a scale of 1 to 5, please indicate how useful you found it to see the text being interpreted in real time thanks to Cassis (1 not at all, 5 very much)

11 replies

On a scale of 1 to 5, please indicate how useful you found the terminological help provided by Cassis (1 not at all, 5 very)

11 replies

Did Cassis help you with any backlogs?

11 replies

Which element of Cassis is the most useful for you?

11 replies

- Real-time text recognition
- Visual input gives a sense of security
- Terminology database

Other useful function

4 replies

Simple interface
the (quite infallible) recognition of numbers
distinguishing terminology hits by colour
Terminology database

What elements of Cassis or the Cassis interface did you NOT get on with?

11 replies

-
I can't see what databases were set up, or at least, how many
did not work
The text as it moves (even changes)
Unfortunately I was not able to use the program during the day.
the terminology database
There is no such element
When it writes something funny.
During the practice, we did not have a terminology database, so I could not test it.
sometimes it still splits my attention to see and hear the text at the same time

How often have you looked at the Cassis surface?

10 replies

What do you see as the weaknesses of Cassis?

11 replies

Not taking advantage of the benefits of artificial intelligence

did not work

a strong accent (when we most need support anyway) unfortunately gets the better of it completely, even though, especially in English, we often interpret for non-native speakers

Speech recognition and speech-to-text transcription are sometimes unreliable.

StT uncertainties

not always precise

It does not punctuate, the text it writes blends together and is not always reliable (sometimes misunderstands what the speaker is saying).

Names, funny misunderstandings, stumbling blocks.

-

It's an additional a factor to pay attention to, so I feel it's necessary to practice it to learn when it's helpful and when it's distracting to have to read the text too.

possible errors. If the machine makes a mistake (e.g. during text recognition), it loses the interpreter's confidence

Would you use Cassis in a live work situation?

11 replies

Justify your answer!

11 replies

Less fatigue on "temporary memory"

did not work

On the one hand, it's great that it recognizes numbers and I like the terminology option; on the other hand, I don't know if I'd risk my performance by dividing my attention even more (with funny mishearings and, as mentioned, the movement)

When used as intended, the program can be a great help, both in catching up on any backlogs, in recalling and synthesising ideas that have been missed, and in using terminology effectively.

tried it

It depends on many things, but if you see a text that is different from the real one, it may distract you from the interpretation

Yes, because it can help with numbers, proper names and terminology.

I think it would help. If I didn't feel it was helping, I wouldn't check it often, but it might be good as a plus.

I don't think that CASSIS could be made available at an affordable price in Hungary for a sole trader. If translation agencies made it available then yes, I would use it.

I'd like to see if the above features really help in a live situation.

if I lose track, it helps me get back on track quickly + numbers + full names

Would you recommend Cassis to others?

11 replies

Justify your decision!

11 replies

I'm sure others will like it too

It worked for my cabin mate once for a short time, and when a number came up, Cassis spelled it correctly, my cabin mate looked at it and could say it straight away, he didn't have to write it down. If it works, it can help when you're behind and suddenly can't remember a key word from, say, a list.

Number recognition, and sometimes even sight-reading, is a big help, and I'm sure some people don't mind the movement

It could greatly help the work of all interpreters, improving the quality of their work.

can also help others

Those who deserve it ;-)

If it's useful to me, it can be useful to others.

I think everyone should try it to see if it helps.

Basically a useful tool.

With constant practice, I think you can learn how it can help you interpret.

for the above reasons

What other features would you find useful in the Cassis interface?

11 replies

AI, BIG data, name recognition

I can't think of anything else

highlighting numbers/data, language recognition

Automatically displaying the meaning of rarely used words and phrases in the target language, possibly based on lists of words that have been compiled in applied linguistic research and classify the frequency of use of each word.

segmentation:)

The whole text should not blend together, a method should be developed to detect punctuation (end of sentence periods, commas, etc.)

Perhaps if you could print out on a separate page the numbers and proper names that are spoken.

Correct names (spelled according to pronunciation, perhaps?)

Highlighting, asterisking function e.g. frequently occurring words, etc.

Optional highlighting of numbers and proper names, so that the interpreter can find the relevant part of the text immediately if he or she only occasionally looks at the screen.

online dictionary (or a combination of several) built-in

Comment (write down anything you didn't know above but would like to)

4 replies

Many times the window would "fill up" and no new text would appear until I refreshed it. This was mainly the case in the morning, but worked quite well in the afternoon workshop. Unfortunately, it didn't give any terminology hits, even though words included in the glossary were spoken (I haven't checked whether it recognised them yet)

-

I didn't use Cassis for interpreting, but for transcribing and correcting video texts. So my answers about interpreting are not really relevant. However, I really think Cassis would be better if there was punctuation and the text didn't flow together so much.

I was interpreting at the event on Friday, so I didn't test CASSIS in real life. I answered the questionnaire based on my previous testing and what I had experienced at the event.

REFERENCES

- Ildikó HORVÁTH: *Bevezetés a tolmácsolás pszichológiájába (Introduction to the Psychology of Interpreting)*, ELTE Eötvös Kiadó , 2015
- Krisztina SZABARI, *Bevezetés a fordítás elméletébe (Introduction to the Theory and Practice of Interpreting)*, Scholastica, Budapest, 1999
- Kinga KLAUDY, *Bevezetés a fordítás elméletébe (Introduction to the Theory of Translation)*, Scholastica, Budapest, 2004
- CHERNOV G. V., *Inference and Anticipation in Simultaneous Interpreting: A Probability-prediction model*, Philadelphia, 2004
- GILE Daniel, *Regards sur la recherche en interprétation de conférence*, Arras: Presses Universitaires de Lille, 1995
- Borbála ROHONYI, *A szöveggel támogatott szinkrontolmácsolás vizsgálata angol-magyar nyelvi irányban (Examination of text-assisted simultaneous interpreting in the English-Hungarian language direction)*, Doctoral School of Linguistics, ELTE, Budapest, 2018
- R., CAMMOUN, C., DAVIES, K., IVANOV, B., NAIMUSHIN, *Simultaneous Interpretation with Text: Is the Text 'Friend' or 'Foe'? Laying Foundations for a Teaching Module*. Observational research paper, 2009
- CHIARO, D. & Nocella, G. (2004) Interpreters' Perception of Linguistic and Non-Linguistic Factors Affecting Quality: A Survey through the World Wide Web. *Meta*, 49(2), 278-293. <https://doi.org/10.7202/009351ar>
- H., LAMBERGER-FELBER, J., SCHNEIDER, *Linguistic interference in simultaneous interpreting with text: a case study*, In: G., HANSEN, A., CHESTERMAN, H., GERZYMISCH-ARBOGAST (eds), *Efforts and Models in Interpreting and Translation Research - A Tribute to Daniel Gile*, Amsterdam and Philadelphia, 2009
- FABBRO, F., L., GRAN, *English Neurological and neuropsychological aspects of polyglossia and simultaneous interpretation* in S., Lambert & B., Moser-Mercer (Eds.), *BRIDGING THE GAP: EMPIRICAL RESEARCH IN SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETATION* (pp. 273-317.), Amsterdam: Benjamins, 1994
- Hitoshi, IIDA, Eiichiro, SUMITA, Osamu, FURUSE, *Spoken-Language Translation Method Using Examples*, *Proceedings of the 16th International Conference on Computational Linguistics*, 1996, Vol. 1, pp. 1074-1077.
- Toshihiko, ITOH, Akihiro, DENDA, Satoru, KOGURE, Seiichi, NAKAGAWA, *A Robust Dialogue System with Spontaneous Speech Understanding and Cooperative*

Response, *Proceedings of the [Interactive Spoken Dialog Systems: Bringing Speech and NLP Together in Real Applications](#)*, 1997, pp. 57-60.

Bühler, H. 1986. linguistic (semantic) and extralinguistic (pragmatic) criteria for the evaluation of conference interpretation and interpreters. *Multilingua* Vol. 5. No. 4. 231-235

Hideki, MIMA, Hitoshi, IIDA, Osamu, FURUSE, *Simultaneous Interpretation Utilizing Example-based Incremental Transfer. Proceedings of the [36th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics and 17th International Conference on Computational Linguistics, Vol. 2](#)*, 1998, pp. 855-861.

Chengqing, ZONG, Bo Xu, TAIYI HUANG, *Interactive Chinese-to-English Speech Translation Based on Dialogue Management. Proceedings of the Workshop on Speech-to-Speech Translation: Algorithms and Systems*, 2002, pp. 61-68

Masamitsu, UMEDA, Satoru, KOGURE, Seiichi, NAKAGAWA, *Interpreter for Highly Portable Spoken Dialogue System. [Proceedings of the Fourth SIGdial Workshop of Discourse and Dialogue](#)*, 2003

Ran, XU, Serge, SHAROFF, *Evaluating Term Extraction Methods for Interpreters. Proceedings of the 4th International Workshop on Computational Terminology*, 2014, pp. 86-93.

Xiaolin, WANG, Andrew, FINCH, Masao, UTIYAMA, Eiichiro, SUMITA, *A Prototype Automatic Simultaneous Interpretation System. Proceedings of COLING 2016, the 26th International Conference on Computational Linguistics: System Demonstrations*, 2016, pp. 30-34.

HEY, Jordan Boyd-Graber, Hal Daumé III, *Interpretese vs. Translatese: The Uniqueness of Human Strategies in Simultaneous Interpretation, Proceedings of NAACL-HLT 2016*, 2016, pp. 971-976.

Olivier, HAMON, Christian, FÜGEN, Djamel, MOSTEFA, Victoria, ARRANZ, Muntsin, KOLSS, Alex, WAIBEL, Khalid, CHOUKRI, *End-to-End Evaluation in Simultaneous Translation. Proceedings of the 12th Conference of the European Chapter of the ACL*, 2009, pp. 345-353.

Malia, SPENCER, *Facebook Acquires Pittsburgh Tech Firm. Pittsburgh Business Times*, Aug 13, 2013.

9: Zsuzsa G. LÁNG, *Tolmácsolás felsőfokon: a hivatásos tolmácsok képzéséről (Interpreting at the top: training professional interpreters)*, Budapest, Scholastica, 2002

ZWISCHENBERGER et al. (2008) Quality and Role: The Professionals' View
Franz, PÖCHHACKER, *Quality Assurance in Simultaneous Interpreting*, in Dollerup, C., Lindegaard, A. (eds.) *Teaching Translating And Interpreting 2 (Insights, Aims, Visions)*, Amsterdam/Philadelphia: John Benjamins, 1994, pp. 232-242.

ZWISCHENBERGER C. and PÖCHHACKER F. (2010) "Survey on quality and role: conference interpreters' expectations and self-perceptions", <http://www.aiic.net/ViewPage.cfm/page3405.htm>

(last accessed 19/07/2010).

Ildikó HORVÁTH, *A fordító- és tolmácsolás új kihívásai (New challenges in translator and interpreter training)*. In: Kinga, Klauzy (ed.) *Fordítás és tolmácsolás a harmadik évezred elején (Translation and Interpretation at the Dawn of the Third Millennium)*, ELTE Eötvös Kiadó, Budapest, 2012, pp. 152-155.

Pablo, SALVADOR PÉREZ, *The use of a corpus management tool for the preparation of interpreting assignments: a case study*. *Translation & Interpreting* Vol. 10, No. 1., 2018, pp. 137-151.

12: N., KELLY, *Moving Toward Machine Interpretation*. *tcworld* January/February 2009, pp. 15-17.

András Kristóf, MÓRICZ, *Információ- és kommunikációtechnológiai eszközök használata a tolmácsolásban (The use of information and communication technology tools in interpreting)*. *Fordítástudomány* Vol. 18. No. 1., 2016, pp. 50-63.

11: A., PYM, *What Technology does to Translating*. *Translation & Interpreting.org*, 2011 (<http://www.trans-int.org/index.php/transint/article/view/121/81>, last consulted August 2018)

Zoltán PAPP, *A tolmácsolás technológiai eszközökkel történő támogatása (Supporting interpretation with technological tools)*. Thesis, Budapest, 2016, BME

10: C., FANTINUOLI, *Computer-assisted interpretation: challenges and future perspectives*. In Durán Muñoz, I. and Corpas Pastor, G. (eds.) *Trends in e-tools and resources for translators and interpreters*, 2018, p.155.

13: H., COSTA, G., CORPAS PASTOR and I., DURÁN-MUÑOZ, *A Comparative User Evaluation of Terminology Management Tools for Interpreters*. In *Proceedings of the Workshop on Computational Terminology (CompuTerm '14), 25th International Conference on Computational Linguistics (COLING '14)*, 2014.

14: H., COSTA, G., CORPAS PASTOR and I., DURÁN-MUÑOZ, *Assessing Terminology Management Systems for Interpreters*. In I., DURÁN-MUÑOZ and G., CORPAS PASTOR (eds.), *Trends in e-tools and resources for translators and interpreters*, 2017, pp. 57-84.

GILE, *Basic Theoretical Components in Interpreter and Translator Training*, in C., Dollerup, and A., Loddegaard (eds), *Teaching Translation and Interpreting: Training, Talent and Experience*, Amsterdam: John Benjamins, 1992, pp. 185-194.

Gergely KOVÁSZNAI, *Párbeszéd rendszerek (Dialogue systems)*, 2012

Ágnes WERNER, *Beszédfelismerés, beszédmegérté (Speech Recognition, Speech Understanding)*, <https://docplayer.hu/17964073-Beszédfelismeres-beszédmegertes.html>

M., Khaled ALHAWITI, *Advances in Artificial Intelligence Using Speech Recognition*, 2015

László DUDÁS, *Alkalmazott Mesterséges Intelligencia (Applied Artificial Intelligence)*, Kempelen Farkas Student Information Centre, 2011

Omid, KASHEFI, *Unsupervised Part-of-Speech Induction*, 2018

S., DORNIC, "The bilingual's performance: language dominance, stress and individual differences", in *Language Interpretation and Communication*. ed. By D., GENVER, & H.W., SINAIKO, New York, Plenum Press, 1978, pp. 259-270.

V., BOSCHIAN SCHIAVON, *Velocità de parola e interpretazione simultanea*, SSLMIT, Serie Monografie, N. 20, Trieste, Università degli Studi di Trieste, 1983

P., KAHL, "Translation quality - how can we tell it's good enough", in *Translating and the Computer* 12. Ed. By C., PICKEN, London, Aslib, 1991, pp. 149-158.

Annalisa, SANDRELLI, Jesús, DE MANUEL JEREZ, *The Impact of Information And Communication Technology on Interpreter Training: State-of-the-art And Future Prospects, The Interpreter And Translator Trainer* Vol. 1. No. 2., 2007, pp. 269-303.

Dániel VÍGH, *THE ASPECTS OF SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETING WITH TEXT. PPKE BTK 2019*

Ádám GYARMATI, *Mesterséges Intelligencia a tolmácsolásban (Artificial Intelligence in Interpreting)*. PPKE BTK 2019.

Benjámín SZILASI, *Computer-assisted interpreting and automatic speech recognition: effects of the CASSIS software on simultaneous interpreting terminology*, University of Vienna 2022.

Noémi FAZEKAS & Krisztina Sarosi-Mardirosz (2021) *Bevezetés a tolmácsolás elméletébe (Introduction to Interpretation Theory)*. Textbook. Scientia Kiadó, Cluj-Napoca. ISBN 978-606-975-042-1 (pages 106-107)

ADDITIONAL RESOURCES

Krisztina SZABARI, *Tolmácsolás. Bevezetés a tolmácsolás elméletébe és gyakorlatába (Interpretation. Introduction to the Theory and Practice of Interpreting)*, Budapest, Scholastica, 2006

- DR. Mária GÓSY, *Pszicholingvisztika (Psycholinguistics)*, Budapest, Osiris Kiadó, 2005
- Claudia, V ANGELELLI & Brian James, BAER, *Experimental research, In (eds) Researching Translation and Interpreting*, Oxon and New York, Routledge, pp. 220-228.
- Karen, KORNING ZETHSEN, *Langauge and communication*, Aarhus, 1999
- GILE DANIEL, *Testing the Effort Models' tightrope hypothesis in simultaneous interpreting*, Hermes, Journal of Linguistics no. 23 - 1999
- Davis, CRYSTAL, *Encyclopaedia of Language*, Osiris, 1998
- Kexiu, YIN, *Disfluencies in Consecutive Interpreting among Undergraduates in the Language Lab Environment. Proceedings of the 5th Pacific Asia Conference on Language, Information and Computation*, 2011, pp. 459-466.
- Alexandra Markó, *A spontán beszéd néhány szupraszegmentális jellegzetessége (Certain suprasegmental features of spontaneous speech)*, PhD thesis, ELTE, 2005
- Sylvia, KALINA, *Quality Assurance for Interpreting Processes, Processus et cheminements en traduction et interprétation*, Volume 50, numéro 2, 2005
- G.A., MILLER et al, *Plans and the Structure of Behavior*, New York, Holt, 1960
- A.D., BADDELEY and G., HITCH, Working memory. In G. A., BOWER (ed.), *The Psychology of Learning and Motivation*, 1974, pp. 48-79.
- D., GILE, *Basic Concepts and Models for Interpreter and Translator Training*, Amsterdam & Philadelphia, John Benjamins, 1995
- Cynthia, JANE, Kellett, BIDOLI, "Quality assessment in conference interpreting - an overview" in *Miscellanea 4*, 2000, pp. 105-145.
- Holly, MIKKELSON, Renée, JOURDENAIS, *The Routledge Handbook of Interpreting*, ed: Routeledge, New York, 2015
- Lourdes, DE RIOJA, "Interpreting quality: global professional standards?" in Ren W. (ed.), *Interpreting in the Age of Globalization: Proceedings of the 8th National Conference and International Forum on Interpreting*, 2013, pp. 305-318.
- Shigeki, MATSUBARA, Katsuhiko TOYAMA, Yasuyoshi INAGAKI, *Sync/Trans: Simultaneous Machine Interpretation between English and Japanese*. In Norman Foo (ed.) *Advanced Topics in Artificial Intelligence (LNAI 1747)*, 1999, pp. 134-143.
- Bakti, M. 2010. *Diszharmóniás jelenségek a szinkrontolmácsok célnyelvi beszédprodukcójában (Discordant phenomena in the speech production of simultaneous interpreters in the target language)*. Doctoral thesis. Budapest: ELTE.
- Bakti, M., Bóna, J. 2014. Source language-related erroneous stress placement in the target language output of simultaneous interpreters. *Interpreting* Vol. 16. no. 1. 34-48.

- Chernov, G.V. 2004. *Inference and Anticipation in Simultaneous Interpreting: A Probability-prediction model*. Philadelphia: John Benjamins.
- Gile, D. 1984. les noms propres en interprétation simultanée. *Multilingua* Vol. 3. No. 2. 79-85.
- Gile, D. 1985. le modèle d'efforts et l'équilibre d'interprétation en interprétation simultanée. *meta* vol. 30. No. 1. 44-48.
- Gile, D. 1990a. Scientific research vs. personal theories in the investigation of interpretation, in Gran, L., Taylor, Ch. (eds) *Aspects of applied and experimental research on conference interpretation*, Udine: Campanotto, 28-41.
- Gile, D. 1990b. L'évaluation de la qualité de l'interprétation par les délégués : une étude de cas. *The Interpreters' Newsletter* No. 3. 66-71.
- Gile, D. 1995a. *Basic Concepts and Models for Interpreter and Translator Training*. Amsterdam and Philadelphia: Benjamins.
- Gile, D. 1995b. *Regards sur la recherche en interprétation de conférence*. Arras : Presses Universitaires de Lille.
- Gile, D. 1997. conference interpreting as a cognitive management problem. in Pöchhacker, F., Shlesinger, M. (eds) 2002. *the interpreting studies reader*. London and New York: Routledge. 162-176.
- Gile, D. 1998: Observational Studies and Experimental Studies in the Investigation of Conference Interpreting. 10. No.1 69-93. 249
- István Szakadát: Egyben az egész egytől egyig, új média remix 2 (All in One, New Media remix 2). Typotex Kiadó, 2007

Gile, D. 1999. Testing the Effort Models' tightrope hypothesis in simultaneous interpreting - A contribution. *Hermes, Journal of Linguistics*. No. 23. 153-172.

Gile, D. 2009a. *Basic Concepts and Models for Interpreter and Translator Training*. Rev.ed. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.

Gile, D. 2009b. Conference Interpreting, historical and cognitive perspectives. In Baker, M., Saldanha, G. (eds) *Routledge Encyclopedia of Translation Studies*. 2nd edition. London and New York: Routledge. 51-56.

I. Horváth, 2013b. 2013b. Gépi tolmácsolás (Machine interpreting). In: J. Dróth (ed.) 2013. Gödöllő: Szent István University, Faculty of Economics and Social Sciences. 106-113.

Korpál, P., Stachowiak, K. 2017. A closer look at numbers in simultaneous interpreting. Poster presented at the *19th European Conference on Eye Movements*. Wuppertal, Germany, August 20-24, 2017.

Judit Navracsecs: A kétnyelvű mentális lexikon és működése (The bilingual mental lexicon and its functioning). Doctoral thesis 2014, Veszprém

Seeber, K. G. 2011. multimodal input in simultaneous interpretation: an eye-tracking experiment. Zybatov, L. N., Petrova, A., Ustaszewski, M. (eds) *Proceedings of the 1st International Conference TRANSLATA, Translation & Interpreting Research: yesterday - today - tomorrow*. Frankfurt: Peter Lang. 341-347.

Seeber, 2011, K. Stachowiak, (NCN) in Poland: UMO - 2015/17/E/HS2/03160

Seeber, K. G. 2017. Interpreting at the European Institutions: faster, higher, stronger. *CLINA: An Interdisciplinary Journal of Translation, Interpreting and Intercultural Communication*, Vol. 3. No. 2. 73-90.

Seeber, K. G. 2015b. Cognitive load in simultaneous interpreting: Measures and methods. In Ehrensberger-Dow, M., Göpferich, S., O'Brien, Sh. (eds) *Interdisciplinarity in Translation and Interpreting Process Research*. Amsterdam and Philadelphia: John Benjamins. 18-35.

Seeber, K. G. 2015c. Cognitive approaches. In Pöchhacker, F. (ed) *Routledge Encyclopedia of Interpreting Studies*, London and New York: Routledge. 56-60.

Seeber, K. G. 2017a. Interpreting at the European Institutions: faster, higher, stronger. *CLINA: An Interdisciplinary Journal of Translation, Interpreting and Intercultural Communication*, Vol. 3. No. 2. 73-90.

Seeber, K. G. 2017b. Multimodal Processing in Simultaneous Interpreting, in Schwieter, J. W., Ferreira, A. *The Handbook of Translation and Cognition*, New York: John Wiley & Sons, 461-475.

Seresi, M. 2017. *Videókonferencia a konferenciatolmácsolás oktatásában: a közvetítő médium hatása a tolmáccsal bővített kommunikációs helyzetre, valamint a pedagógiai folyamatra (Video conferencing in conference interpreting education: the impact of the mediating medium on the communicative situation augmented by the interpreter and the pedagogical process)*. Doctoral dissertation. Budapest: ELTE.

Seresi, M. 2016, *Távtolmácsolás és távoktatás a tolmácsképzésben (Distance Interpreting and Distance Learning in Interpreter Education)*, ELTE Eötvös Kiadó
K. Stachowiak, (NCN) in Poland: UMO - 2015/17/E/HS2/03160

Teodora Cekic <https://prezi.com/65xwum9p1oym/a-tolmacskepzes-kezdetei/>
2017-10-13.

Krisztina Szabari: *Bevezetés a tolmácsolás elméletébe és gyakorlatába (Introduction to the Theory and Practice of Interpreting)*, Scholastica, Budapest, 1999

Kinga Klaudy: *Bevezetés a fordítás elméletébe (Introduction to Translation Theory)*, Scholastica, Budapest, 2004

Chernov G. V., *Inference and Anticipation in Simultaneous Interpreting: A Probability-prediction model*, Philadelphia, 2004

Gile Daniel, *Regards sur la recherche en interprétation de conférence*, Arras: Presses Universitaires de Lille, 1995

Seleskovitch, D., Lederer, M. 2002. *Pédagogie raisonnée de l'interprétation*. 2ème édition corrigée et augmentée. Paris : Didier Érudition

Zsolt Robotka https://www.signall.us/product_info/ 2022

Lili Sotkovszky: *A tolmácsolás jövője technológiai szempontból (The future of interpreting from a technological point of view)*, Thesis BME 2017

Alhawiti M., Khaled, *Advances in Artificial Intelligence Using Speech Recognition*, 2015

Endre Kiss ComputerWorld 2017, <https://computerworld.hu/tech/melytanulas-mitosz-es-valosag-239725.html>

Bálint Pál Tóth, *Élet és Tudomány* 15/09/2016, Beszélő számítógépek mély gondolatokkal (Talking computers with deep thoughts)
<https://eletstudomany.hu/neuralis-halozatok-beszelo-szamitogepek-mely-gondolatokkal/>

INTERNET RESOURCES

[Allison Burkette](#), [William A. Kretzschmar Jr](#): Big Data: Using a Corpus, Cambridge University Press, 2018.

<https://www.birmingham.ac.uk/news/thebirminghambrief/items/2017/08/linguistics-in-the-digital-age.aspx> /2018.07.25./

<https://www.quora.com/How-can-I-apply-neural-networks-in-big-data> /2018.07.22./

<https://corplinguistics.wordpress.com/?s=big+data&submit=Search> /2018.07.25./

https://www.sas.com/fr_fr/insights/big-data/what-is-big-data.html /2018.07.20./

<http://www.eu-bridge.eu/communication.html> /2018.07.25./

Harry, HOGU, *The History of Simultaneous Interpretation*

<http://translationexcellence.com/?s=The+History+of+Simultaneous+Interpretation>

http://www.emcinterpreting.org/?q=system/files/EMCI_Quality_Assurance_Standards.pdf

https://ec.europa.eu/info/departments/interpretation_en, 04/09/2018.

<https://aiic.net>

Noam, CHOMSKY, *"Tool Module: Chomsky's Universal Grammar"*. Retrieved 2010-10-07

LECTURES, CONFERENCES

- 28-29 September 2018 Budapest "FIT-FOR-MARKET TRANSLATOR AND INTERPRETER TRAINING IN A DIGITAL AGE" section 2: New technologies and tools in translation and interpreting: *computer-assisted interpreting systems*
- 30-31 October 2018 Budapest "MEET Central Europe" Central European regional conference of the language industry: CASSIS Katalin Hajós - Péter Klein
- 21-22 February 2019 Barcelona "Together Elia's freelancer and language company event" CASSIS Katalin Hajós
- 23-24 August 2019 Budapest "National Professional Forum of Interpreters and Translators" *The future of interpreting - what technology will bring* Lili Sotkovszky
- 30-31 May 2019 Budapest "MEMOQ Fest" CASSIS
- 22-23 September 2019 Budapest "National Professional Forum of Translators and Interpreters" Katalin Hajós
- 15-16 November 2019 Budapest SZOKOE "Teaching and researching professional language in an international context" Patrícia Beták - Katalin Hajós: CASSIS, the magic potion of the 21st century interpreter
- 11-12 May 2020 Budapest "Online Translator Days" Kata Hajós: Cassis - artificial intelligence to support interpreters